

Database of Relevant Projects and Initiatives

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Deliverable 1.4

Transforming and Inspiring
Aquatic Landscapes Through
Art and Science

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Use of this database

The purpose of TIDAL ArtS database of Relevant Project and Initiatives is for the consortium members' to deepen the connections with EU initiatives such as Mission Ocean, Culture Europe, and the New European Bauhaus activities. The mapping offers 155 projects (including active and finished projects organised in a descending order) searched through CORDIS database, Culture and Creativity as well as ERASMUS+, New European Bauhaus websites and Google search engine. During the mapping process a Workshop session titled "Where Art Meets Science. For Our Ocean and Waters." was organized. On 23rd of January (2025) 30 relevant initiatives (marked in green in the respective database sheet) joined TIDAL ArtS team for a two hour long workshop. The session offered dialogue on questions regarding barriers and opportunities, negative and positive aspects when art+science+ocean is merged, impact related as well as participatory element discussions. This exchange allows to gain insights of existing practices and thus ensure that TIDAL ArtS efforts are not duplicated. The database with the complimentary workshop fosters the synchronisation, alignment and synergies between the other initiatives and their activities. The deliverable serves as a building block for WP2-5 for further exchange.

List of acronyms used in the database

Accelerator grants	Funding programme under Horizon Europe funded projects
ERASMUS+	The EU's programme to support education, training, youth and sport in Europe
ERC	European Research Council
HORIZON	Horizon2020 or HorizonEurope funded projects
N/A	Not applicable
N/D	No data
MO	Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030' part of Horizon Europe funded projects
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
Other	Publications, awards, prizes, national funding sources

No	Project acronym and full title	Abstract and source	Timeline (descending order)	Funding source: Mission Ocean (MO), Horizon, accelerator grants, other (e.g. publication)	Coordinating institution
1	iNNO SED: iNNOvative SEDiment management in the Danube River Basin	<p>"Navigating sediment challenges in the Danube River Basin. The management of sediment in the Danube River Basin presents a critical environmental challenge. The alteration of sediment balance has become a pressing issue, decreasing habitat quality, increasing natural hazards, and worsening navigational conditions. Furthermore, industries, urban centres and agriculture require thorough sediment quality evaluations, but standardised monitoring is lacking. In response, the EU-funded iNNO SED project aims to launch the Danube Sediment 'Lighthouse' Knowledge Centre and to develop a Sediment Management Toolbox. These will boost our understanding of problems related to sediment quantity and quality, and will foster innovative solutions. By collaborating with stakeholders and Associated Regions, iNNO SED will also serve as a model for global river systems. The project aligns with the EU's mission to bolster competitiveness". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157360</p>	2024-2029	MO	BUDAPESTI MUSZAKI ES GAZDASAGTUDOMANYI EGYETEM, Hungary
2	PHAROS: Lighthouse for Atlantic and Arctic Basin	<p>"Pioneering solutions for ocean health and sustainability. The health of our oceans is increasingly under threat from pollution, habitat degradation, and the urgent need for sustainable economic practices. The EU has set ambitious targets to protect marine ecosystems, reduce pollution, and achieve a carbon-neutral blue economy by 2030. However, bridging the gap between setting these goals and implementing effective solutions remains a challenge. The EU-funded PHAROS project is set to pioneer innovative approaches in ocean management. Specifically, it aims to bridge the crucial phases of development and deployment, leveraging new technologies and partnerships to meet the EU's Ocean Mission objectives effectively. PHAROS will conduct three demonstrations in the Atlantic using natural-based solutions and integrated multi-trophic aquaculture, tailored to specific regional needs". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157936</p>	2024-2029	MO	CONSORCIO PARA EL DISENO, CONSTRUCCION, EQUIPAMIENTO Y EXPLOTACION DE LA PLATAFORMA OCEANICA DE CANARIAS, Spain
3	BLUE CONNECT: Strict protection, restoration and co-management of Marine Protected Areas to ensure effective ecosystem conservation and improved connectivity of Blue Corridors	<p>"The BLUE CONNECT project addresses the urgent need to protect and restore marine habitats and ecosystems and to reach ambitious EU and global protection and restoration targets by 2030. Together with Marine Protected Area (MPA) managers, authorities, industries, and local communities from 12 Demonstration sites and beyond, BLUE CONNECT is co-developing, promoting, and demonstrating a systematic approach to marine conservation planning and management. This collaborative effort will result in the creation of a powerful Blueprint, directly supporting 1) setting science-based conservation objectives, 2) co-defining conservation actions for effective MPA co-management, 3) ensuring conservation effectiveness and 4) demonstrating the high potential of these tools for replicability and broader use. This will be made possible by establishing a holistic modelling framework that integrates various elements of biodiversity, ecological functioning, ecosystem services, and connectivity, while also considering inputs from stakeholders and local communities regarding social, economic, and cultural aspects when defining MPAs and ecological corridors. The project will contribute to a more comprehensive, science-based and inclusive approach to designating new MPAs or expanding existing ones, transitioning to strict protection, restoring ecosystems, enhancing ecological connectivity, and facilitating MPA co-management. By fostering just and fair stakeholder cooperation and citizen science initiatives, BLUE CONNECT will build a greater feeling of co-ownership of protected and restored marine ecosystems and MPA networks and empower communities to play a crucial role in safeguarding our seas". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156759</p>	2024-2028	MO	SUBMARINER NETWORK FOR BLUE GROWTH EWIV, Germany
4	SUNDANSE: Innovative sediment management framework for a SustainNable DANube black SEa system	<p>"An ecological boost for the Danube River. In recent decades, the Danube River has faced increasing challenges from human interventions and climate change, disrupting its natural balance and posing risks to both ecosystems and communities. The EU-funded SUNDANSE project will address these issues head-on. Specifically, it will analyse and mitigate environmental impacts in the Danube River basin. Using advanced technology and innovative methodologies, the project will map critical sedimentation points, develop predictive models for sediment transport, and pioneer portable equipment for real-time analysis of microplastics and toxicity. By enhancing cooperation and governance across sectors, SUNDANSE strives to foster sustainable management practices that restore the Danube's ecological health and resilience". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156533</p>	2024-2028	MO	UNIVERSITATEA DUNAREA DE JOS DIN GALATI, Romania

5	BioProtect: Advancing area-based management tools to accelerate the protection and restoration of marine biodiversity across the European sea basins	"Innovative solutions to restore biodiversity in European seas. Human activities and climate change are causing ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss. Previous approaches, which focused on sector-based management in isolation and single spatial scales, have failed to halt biodiversity loss. The EU-funded BioProtect project aims to develop innovative ecosystem-based solutions for protecting and restoring biodiversity in European seas. It will use the ABM-DSF framework to engage stakeholders, monitor biodiversity changes, map human pressures, prioritise areas for protection and restoration, and measure ecological and socio-economic impacts. The project will demonstrate these solutions in five sites ranging from the Arctic to the Atlantic. It will consider 'what-if' scenarios, including climate change, protection strategies, and their impacts. The consortium possesses expertise in both the Atlantic and Arctic basins". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157341	2024-2028	MO	MATIS OHF, Iceland
6	EUROLakes: IntEgrated protection and Restoration appRoches for natUral Lake EcoSystems	"Nature-based solutions to restore European lakes. Pollution has greatly damaged European lakes, necessitating new solutions and actions to protect and restore their health. The EU-funded EUROLakes project aims to protect and restore European natural lakes and their ecosystems. It is based on the 4 Returns Framework for Landscape Restoration, seeking sustainable, long-term solutions at the landscape level. The project will work with local communities to develop integrated protection and restoration strategies, focusing on nature-based solutions in three specific areas: Lake Vico in Italy, Lake Bistreț in Romania, and Lake Dümmer in Germany. The project's goals align with various EU instruments and policies, including the Water Framework Directive and the Green Deal". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157482	2024-2028	MO	WETLANDS INTERNATIONAL - EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION, The Netherlands
7	FERRO: Fostering European lakes restoration by nutrient removal, recovery, and reuse: integrated catchment and in-lake scale approach	"Circular management approach for European lakes restoration. Climate change exacerbates eutrophication in European lakes, but it could also help address the depletion of global phosphate reserves, which threatens global food security. The influx of nutrients into lakes leads to nutrient-rich reserves and frequent algal blooms. The EU-funded FERRO project aims to tackle nutrient enrichment and phosphate depletion in lakes using a circular management approach. It will develop an innovative lake restoration method that combines targeted techniques with nutrient recovery and recycling. The project is set to improve the ecological status of lakes, support a circular economy, enhance climate adaptation, and promote biodiversity. FERRO will prioritise lake restoration and implement sustainable solutions to prevent nutrient losses in agriculture". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157743	2024-2028	MO	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR UMWELTFORSCHUNG GMBH - UFZ, Germany
8	ProCleanLakes: Integrated emerging approaches for joint protection and restoration of Natural Lakes in the spirit of European life heritage support	"Innovative solutions to preserve Europe's natural lakes. Natural lakes across Europe face mounting challenges from chemical contaminants and nutrient enrichment, exacerbated by various human activities. These pressures degrade ecosystem health, threatening biodiversity and water quality. In this context, the EU-funded ProCleanLakes project addresses this crisis by developing integrated nature-based solutions. It aims to restore and protect European Natural Lakes (ENL) through innovative approaches that harmonise economic, environmental, and social interests. Specifically, the project applies transdisciplinary approaches across multiple affected sites to demonstrate scalable solutions. An innovative support platform merges AI and citizen science, empowering communities in lake protection and restoration. ProCleanLakes pioneers tools like mobile decision support systems and AI analytics, ensuring a holistic impact and replicability across Europe's natural lake ecosystems". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157886	2024-2028	MO	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
9	SEAGLOW: Sustainable Energy Applications for Green and Low-impact Operation of small-scale fishing boats in the Baltic and North Sea basins	"Innovative tech for cleaner seas. The small-scale fishing industry in the North and Baltic Sea basins faces significant challenges due to high fossil fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. In this context, the EU-funded SEAGLOW project aims to demonstrate and compare five innovative technologies designed to reduce the environmental impact of fishing vessels. By equipping boats with hybrid electric drivetrains, methanol-powered engines, advanced polymer-based surface coatings, and low-cost permanent sensors, SEAGLOW will collect data to refine these applications. The technologies will be tested on four vessels ranging from 8.5 to 11.5 tonnes across Denmark, Estonia, Norway, and Sweden. The project's goal is to decrease the ecological footprint of these vessels, promoting sustainable fishing practices in the region". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157477	2024-2028	MO	NORDDANMARKS EU-KONTOR, Denmark

10	SpongeWorks: Co-creating and Upscaling Sponge Landscapes by Working with Natural Water Retention and Sustainable Management	"Creating sponge landscapes for climate resilience. As climate change intensifies, landscapes across Europe must adapt to the changing frequency and intensity of floods and droughts. Traditional water management practices are often inadequate and can even exacerbate these growing challenges, making it essential to adopt nature-based solutions. The EU-funded SpongeWorks addresses this need by evaluating and implementing sponge measures and developing sponge strategies as landscape-level approaches that harness nature for improved water retention while providing a range of co-benefits. The project aims to assess and scale up these solutions to strengthen interconnected soil, groundwater, and surface water systems. Through collaboration with local stakeholders and the integration of best practices, SpongeWorks aims to transform landscape management and enhance climate resilience across Europe". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156116	2024-2028	MO	GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER, Germany
11	Path4Med: Demonstrating innovative pathways addressing water and soil pollution in the Mediterranean Agro-Hydro-System	"Sustainable agriculture solutions to tackle Mediterranean nutrient pollution. Water and soil nutrient pollution in the Mediterranean basin poses a grave threat to both ecosystems and human health. Intensive agricultural practices, coupled with inadequate waste management, have led to severe pollution of vital resources. This endangers biodiversity, disrupts food chains, and compromises the quality of drinking water. Addressing this crisis requires innovative and sustainable solutions. The EU-funded Path4Med project aims to tackle these issues by focusing on creating pathways to improve soil health and eliminate water and soil pollution through advanced agricultural management and new monitoring technologies. Path4Med will implement solutions at large-scale demonstration sites and use a digital platform for data exchange and public engagement. Ultimately, the project seeks to ensure a sustainable future for the Mediterranean Sea". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156867	2024-2028	MO	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
12	SEACURE: Innovative solutions to prevent, reduce and remediate nutrient pollution along the land-river-sea system in the Mediterranean basin	"Combating nutrient pollution in the Mediterranean. Nutrient pollution from agricultural activities and inadequate wastewater treatment is wreaking havoc on water quality, soil health, and biodiversity in the Mediterranean Sea basin. Excess nutrients contribute to soil degradation, eutrophication, algal blooms, and ecosystem imbalances worldwide. Addressing this issue requires an approach that spans landscapes, rivers, and seas. The EU-funded SEACURE project will demonstrate and scale up innovative solutions for nutrient management to prevent, reduce, and remediate nutrient pollution through sustainable land practices, improved wastewater treatment, and nature restoration actions. The project will focus on six regions in Spain, Italy, and Greece. SEACURE will also act on governance levers to upscale the effective strategies at regional level and replicate them across the Mediterranean and other sensitive European basins". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157327	2024-2028	MO	FUNDACIO UNIVERSITARIA BALMES, Spain
13	DIGI4ECO: Digital Twin-sustained 4D ecological monitoring of restoration in fishery depleted areas	"Digital twin technology for ecological monitoring. The rapid advancement of digital technologies such as digital twins, AI and machine learning has opened up promising avenues for ecological actions, including conservation, research and restoration. These technologies offer improved monitoring capabilities that can enhance our understanding of ecological processes and biodiversity. The EU-funded DIGI4ECO project aims to develop a digital twin-sustained 4D ecological monitoring system made by networks of robotic platforms, tailored for restoration efforts in fishery-depleted areas. Additionally, the project intends to enhance data flow safety, security and efficiency by developing innovative methodologies and providing toolsets to ensure data trustworthiness. Finally, DIGI4ECO aims to ensure accessibility of the data and demonstrate and enhance the effectiveness of its system". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112883	2024-2028	MO	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain
14	BlueLightS: EnLIGHTening future Schools to deliver BLUE Sustainability in Europe	"Implementing blue education at European schools. The cost-effective implementation of the next phase of Mission Ocean upscaling will require a focus on blue education in Europe. The EU-funded BlueLightS project aims to increase the incorporation of blue challenges into school curricula and the participation of accredited blue schools in the European Blue School network. It promotes the inclusive principles of the EU Green Deal and diversifies the inclusion of blue schools, encompassing schools from inland territories, vocational institutions, and those catering to children with disabilities. The project enhances the quality of blue education initiatives by applying principles of open schooling and citizenship education. It mobilises education stakeholders to experiment with a blue education framework. BlueLightS is developing activities in nine 'experimentation' countries". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101113043	2024-2027	MO	ACTEON SARL, France

15	FutureLakes: Integrating Innovations for the Protection and Restoration of European Lakes	<p>"A blueprint for sustainably reviving Europe's lakes. At the heart of Europe's freshwater ecosystems lies a pressing challenge: restoring the ecological and chemical health of its lakes. In this context, the EU-funded FutureLakes project aims to revolutionise lake restoration and management. To rejuvenate six major European lakes, the project will pioneer the use of nature-based, circular blue economy, and biodiversity-focused solutions. This endeavour aims to restore biodiversity and improve water quality, as well as strengthen societal resilience against climate change. At its core, FutureLakes seeks to create a blueprint for effective lake management, bolstered by public engagement and establishing a blue economy. By scaling up these strategies across Europe, FutureLakes charts a course towards the sustainable use of freshwater, aligning closely with the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156425</p>	2024-2027	MO	NORSK INSTITUTT FOR VANNFORSKNING, Norway
16	REFEST: Retrofitting of fishing fleets with low payback time and easy to deploy solutions for footprint and GHG emissions reduction	<p>"Innovative solutions for greener fishing vessels. Traditional fishing ships face high fuel costs and significant greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. These issues threaten both the environment and the economic viability of the fishing industry. Many current solutions are expensive and complex to implement. Affordable, easy-to-install technologies are needed. To address this issue, the EU-funded REFEST project will develop scalable, low-cost solutions for traditional fishing vessels. REFEST aims to reduce fuel consumption and GHG emissions by 40 %. Innovations include improved hull designs, air lubrication systems, hybrid propulsion, and recyclable materials. The project will test these technologies on three fishing ships in the North Sea and Baltic Sea, preparing for wider deployment by 2029". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157663</p>	2024-2027	MO	KLAIPEDOS UNIVERSITETAS, Lithuania
17	NiD4OCEAN: Nature-inclusive Designs For Reconciling Offshore Renewables With Ocean Protection	<p>"Innovative solutions for offshore renewables. The expansion of offshore renewable energy is crucial for achieving carbon neutrality, but it often conflicts with marine biodiversity preservation. Traditional infrastructure can harm marine habitats, disrupt ecosystems and pose threats to wildlife. Balancing energy needs with environmental protection is a challenge for policymakers and industry leaders. There is a need for innovative solutions that support both sustainable energy and biodiversity goals. The EU-funded NiD4OCEAN project addresses this by advancing nature-inclusive designs (NiDs) and nature-based solutions (NBS) for offshore renewables. Targeting the North Sea, Baltic Sea and Western Mediterranean, the project will develop effective, context-dependent strategies for wind and floating solar structures. Through transdisciplinary collaboration, NiD4OCEAN aims to create tools, frameworks and policies that promote biodiversity and sustainable energy". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156861</p>	2024-2027	MO	NORSK INSTITUTT FOR VANNFORSKNING, Norway
18	Sun-Bio: Sustainable and nature inclusive offshore energy with the parallel biodiversity flourishing, protection and monitoring	<p>"Protecting marine biodiversity while expanding offshore renewable energy capacity. The EU's offshore renewable energy strategy includes ocean protection and biodiversity preservation and restoration. Innovative approaches are needed to produce clean energy and reduce the impact of offshore infrastructures, enhancing their positive effects on the marine environment. The EU-funded Sun-Bio project aims to develop innovative situ ecological monitoring technologies and data collection approaches to support these goals, promoting innovative ways to mitigate infrastructure presence based on restoration. It brings together experts in naval engineering and design, marine ecologists, as well as trustworthy data analytics and relevant intelligence, chemical measurement and spectroscopic methods for sensing, platforms navigation, communication and remote control. Technologies will be designed with users to ensure their larger usability and acceptance, protecting Europe's marine environments while expanding its offshore renewable energy capacity". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157493</p>	2024-2027	MO	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain

19	ECOTWIN: Emulating complex causal socio-ecological models in digital twins of ocean	<p>"To fully realise the potential of the European Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) to empower citizens, entrepreneurs, scientists and policymakers with accessible knowledge about ocean and coastal domains, new models, tools and methods are needed to understand and assess the complex interactions of social, economic and ecological factors. ECOTWIN delivers innovative graph theoretic solutions, developed using a multi-actor approach with policy makers, local communities, marine and coastal industries and communities, to address the challenges of modelling marine socio-ecological systems and integrating these models into the emerging DTO framework. Innovations include four different classes of novel socio-ecological models based on concepts from mathematics (graph theory), control engineering (stability), computer science (generative AI), statistics (Bayesian theory) and information science (entropy), combined with dynamic participatory feedback from stakeholders, and methodological protocols enabling seamless integration with DTOs by accounting for the interoperability, accessibility, reliability and sustainability of transdisciplinary data. The models comprise: 1) quantitative causal graph theoretic models, 2) qualitative causal graph theoretic models, 3) network models with participatory feedback and 4) parallel generative AI models. Through validation in four use cases in the North Sea (Belgium, Germany), Celtic Sea (Ireland), Thracian Sea (Greece) and Waterford Harbour (Ireland), tools will be developed for assessing scenarios including the relationships between factors including ecosystem services and health, geopolitical factors, fishing job losses, tourism and marine renewables development. Results will enable what-if scenario analysis and impact assessments, exploring the interconnected impacts of environmental changes, human pressures and policy implementation to empower better decision-making to support ocean health social prosperity and a thriving blue economy". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157369</p>	2024-2027	MO	<p>THE PROVOST, FELLOWS, FOUNDATION SCHOLARS & THE OTHER MEMBERS OF BOARD, OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY & UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN, Ireland</p>
20	SEADITO: Social-Ecological Analysis and Models for Digital Twin Ocean	<p>"Advancing EU ocean restoration. The EU mission to restore our ocean and waters (Mission Ocean) aims to protect and restore the health of our marine and freshwater environments by 2030 through research and innovation, citizen engagement, and blue investments. The European Digital Twin Ocean (EU DTO) supports this mission. The EU-funded SEADITO project, responding to the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-8, aims to develop analytical methods and tools to support the EU DTO. The project will integrate social-ecological models to establish a decision-support platform for improving ecosystem-based management. It will use case studies in the Baltic, North Sea, Mediterranean, and a Pan-European context. The objective is to develop DTO-compliant decision-support components, scalable social-ecological models, and educational materials for various stakeholders". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157243</p>	2024-2027	MO	<p>AALBORG UNIVERSITET, Denmark</p>
21	SEADOTs: Social-Ecological ocean management Applications with Digital Ocean Twins	<p>"SEADOTs (Social-Ecological Ocean Management Applications using Digital Ocean Twins) has the objective of advancing holistic, just and sustainable ocean management by bringing a predictive component for social-ecological aspects into comprehensive digital ocean twins (DOTs). These DOTs will combine digital twins of the ocean (DTO) with human activities in the ocean and combine socio-ecological and socio-economic data with ocean data, ecosystem data, and a variety of models. By creating and demonstrating applications in the Norwegian North Sea, the Southern North Sea and the Baltic Sea that address current challenges and developments and can simulate the intricate interactions between human activities and marine ecosystems, SEADOTs aims to facilitate and inform political decision making, marine spatial planning and adaptive management. SEADOTs ambition is to help safeguard ocean ecosystems, promote sustainable resource use, and enhance social and economic well-being. The project will leverage developments from ongoing Mission and Green Deal projects where partners are involved in, including the European Digital Twin projects Iliad and EDITO, OLAMUR and CLIMAREST and demonstrate Ocean Management Applications with Digital Ocean Twins on the EU Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) infrastructure as well as distributed platforms for socio-ecological, socio-economic and political endpoints. For that purpose will SEADOTs work with data acquisition and beyond the state of the art and the objective to provide spatially-explicit social-ecological data and data interoperability with geospatial ocean data also after the project period in suitable repositories, through stakeholder capacity building and through collaboration with the co-funded projects of this call. The SEADOTS consortium was built across scientific and technical excellence and is accompanied by an Advisory Board that spans marine spatial planning, political aspects, gaming and social science as well as Ocean Best Practices". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156488</p>	2024-2027	MO	<p>SINTEF OCEAN AS, Norway</p>

22	SURIMI: Integration of innovative and reliable socio-ecological models and user-driven solutions into the Digital Twin Ocean, to facilitate what-if scenarios and decision support, under a co-creation approach	"Advanced tools for sustainable marine management. Marine ecosystems face increasing pressures from human activities, climate change, and pollution, complicating efforts to manage these environments sustainably. Current management strategies often lack comprehensive data integration and user-friendly tools for effective policy analysis. The complexity of socio-ecological interactions in marine systems requires advanced models and harmonised data to inform decision-making. Diverse stakeholders critically need interoperable solutions for efficient marine resource management. The EU-funded SURIMI project addresses these challenges by developing social-ecological models and user-friendly solutions integrated within the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO). Its toolbox will offer open-source models, harmonised data, and AI-driven policy analysis tools, engaging stakeholders to enhance the DTO". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157456	2024-2027	MO	NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE AS, Norway
23	Mr.Goodfish3.0: Co-creating solutions for sustainable seafood consumption	"An app to empower sustainable seafood choices. Overfishing and unsustainable seafood consumption threaten marine ecosystems and biodiversity. Many consumers lack the knowledge to choose seafood that supports sustainable practices. Additionally, socio-cultural and economic factors further complicate efforts to promote responsible consumption. The need for an accessible solution is urgent. With this in mind, the EU-funded Mr.Goodfish3.0 will upgrade an existing app developed with input from the seafood value chain. To promote sustainable seafood consumption, this app will be part of an EU-wide campaign offering personalised decision trees, health benefits, food waste tips, recipes, and good practices. Co-created with stakeholders, the campaign aims to engage the public through social media, educational activities, and collaborations with European initiatives like #TasteTheOcean". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156189	2024-2027	MO	CMMI CYPRUS MARINE AND MARITIME INSTITUTE, Cyprus
24	PartArt4OW: Participatory Art for Society Engagement with Ocean and Water	"Participatory art for society engagement with ocean and water. As oceans and waters are at risk, increased public awareness is crucial. Artistic and creative communities can significantly contribute to protecting our waters. The EU-funded PartArt4OW project aims to connect society with the oceans and waters, raise awareness of the challenges they face, and build a network of artistic communities to support sustainable ocean and water policies. It focuses on participatory art and creative processes, supporting 19 multi-stakeholder Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs) and offering resources and activities to enhance their impact. The project will provide physical resources, human capital (including training), and organisational capital (including planning and monitoring) to selected PAIs through the PartArt4OW Accelerator Programme. It also organises stakeholder engagement, PartArt Sailing Lab activities and ecosystem building". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157247	2024-2027	MO	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA, Italy
25	TIDAL Arts: Transforming and Inspiring Aquatic Landscapes through Art and Sciences	"Art and sciences to protect and restore aquatic landscapes. Climate change and biodiversity crises are having a catastrophic impact on the ocean and inland waters. Creative, interdisciplinary approaches involving citizens are urgently needed to help us think out of the box to solve these challenges. In this context, the EU-funded TIDAL Arts project aims to address environmental and biodiversity crises by uniting art, science, and communities to raise awareness and inspire creative solutions for protecting and restoring our ocean and inland waters. The core of the project will be the implementation of four open calls for artists to co-develop artistic works with scientists, citizens and non-human actors. The project seeks to challenge the traditional separation of nature and culture, by inspiring the participants and individuals who interact with the produced art works to take action for our ocean and waters". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157796	2024-2027	MO	SUBMARINER NETWORK FOR BLUE GROWTH EWIV, Germany
26	TRANSEATION: Advancing Ecosystem-Based Management through Hybrid Blue-Grey Infrastructures in Marine and Coastal Areas	"Hybrid blue-grey infrastructures for marine and coastal ecosystem. Hybrid approaches combining blue-grey infrastructures are increasingly used in marine and coastal environments. The EU-funded TRANSEATION project aims to showcase the benefits of marine and coastal hybrid blue-grey infrastructures. It will also validate the effectiveness of a new level of ecosystem-based management that combines social implication digitalisation and nature-based solutions (NbS) to protect and restore the health and services of marine ecosystems. This management approach integrates hybrid NbS to address societal challenges. It intends to demonstrate the effectiveness of three types of hybrid solutions, identify limiting factors, gaps, and current issues of existing LEED initiatives, analyse the benefits of hybrid solutions, and develop digital solutions for monitoring, analysis, and social involvement". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135343	2024-2027	HORIZON	ASOCIACION CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO NAVAL Y DEL MAR, Spain
27	H2-SEAS: Coastal Fishing Vessels Powered by Zero Emission Hydrogen Fuel Cell	"Hydrogen-electric vessel for zero-emission small-scale fishing fleets. HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-05 promotes ocean protection. Green and energy-efficient small-scale fishing fleets can significantly reduce sea pollution. In this context, the EU-funded H2-SEAS project aims to develop a hydrogen-electric fishing vessel for small-scale fishing fleets, powered by hydrogen fuel cell technology, offering increased energy efficiency and zero emissions. The project involves collaboration between the Latvian Maritime Academy, the Latvian shipyard AtoZ, and Genevos, a French SME. Research activities will assess the regulatory and environmental aspects of the initiative. The project aims to promote hydrogen fuel cell technology for small-scale fishing ships in line with the objectives of the European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157530	2024-2026	MO	RIGAS TEHNISKA UNIVERSITATE, Latvia

28	IDEATION: InlanD watErs in the digitAI Twin Ocean	"IDEATION (InlanD watErs in the digitAI Twin Ocean) aims to prepare the development of the digital twin of the inland waters (rivers, lakes, reservoirs, wetlands, snow, and ice) addressing activities to be developed and to make it integrated and interoperable with the DTO for a unified digital twin of ocean and waters (addressing the hydrosphere as a whole). IDEATION will be based on a cross-border cooperation, involvement, and commitment of stakeholders at European level by following the Water-oriented Living Labs (WoLLs) approach. Stakeholders will be engaged via Multi-Stakeholder Forums (MSF), using a range of different engagement methodologies (e.g. focus groups, workshops, interviews, questionnaires) depending on goals of the engagement and specificities of the context. A comprehensive review will be performed to make an open knowledge inventory for inland water systems (OpenKIWAS). IDEATION will co-design the IDEATION reference architecture defining a set of building blocks, interfaces and standards to make data, models and technologies interoperable and integrable with the DTO. Putting together all the results from the MSF, OpenKIWAS, and the IDEATION reference architecture, a roadmap for the integration of inland waters in the Digital Twin Ocean will be created providing a preliminary breakdown of the work, with priorities of implementation, into a stepped approach. The consortium members have high experience on EU project coordination and participation, the majority of them already worked together in research projects". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101157371	2024-2026	MO	CETAQUA, CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DEL AGUA, FUNDACION PRIVADA, Spain
29	VeriFish: The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns	"Empowering citizens towards sustainable seafood practices. Informed consumer decisions are crucial for sustainable living, yet navigating seafood consumption complexities is challenging. Without standardised information on health, sustainability and climate impacts, consumers struggle to make informed choices. The VeriFish project addresses these challenges by developing a verifiable indicator framework for consumers, retailers, policymakers and fishermen. This framework clarifies seafood's health benefits, climate impacts, and sustainability. VeriFish offers guidelines on using and visualising these indicators, a prototype mobile-friendly application and media products to promote informed choices. In addition, the project will deliver a European Good Practice recommendation as a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) for effective communication about sustainable seafood. VeriFish aims to empower citizens towards sustainable seafood practices through collaborative efforts". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101156426	2024-2026	MO	TRUST-IT SERVICES SRL, Italy
30	ScienceUs: Integration of citizen SCIENCE best practices to Upscale and maximise projects impact related to Green Deal and EU missions	"Paving the way for a European citizen science network. Citizen science involves the participation of the public in carrying out scientific research. Consequently, citizen scientists play a significant role in designing experiments, collecting data and analysing results. The EU-funded ScienceUs project aims to establish a network of European citizen science projects. The project will offer a support programme that includes funding and services to a selection of promising citizen science initiatives. Through communication, dissemination and knowledge transfer strategies, ScienceUs aims to engage all stakeholders. It will create toolkits, training materials and methodologies to promote best practices in citizen science. Additionally, it will establish a network of interconnected citizen science initiatives and foster the interest of funding bodies in supporting sub-projects". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101132113	2024-2026	HORIZON	UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE MADRID, Spain
31	Collaborations for Future - Foundation We Are	"(...) Collaborations for Future: The Blueprints dives into this question, offering a practical guide for designing impactful collaborations. Drawing from nine months of insights, it highlights how creative and scientific expertise can align to tackle climate challenges. Packed with real-world methodologies, it reveals what conditions foster success and why open-ended collaboration sparks innovation. Whether you're starting fresh or rethinking old approaches, this guide is your roadmap for meaningful change". Source: https://collaborationsforfuture.com/	2024-2025	other	Foundation We Are
32	"OceanArt: Science to Art"	"In this exhibition, scientists and artists come together to increase awareness about the problems the Ocean faces, to achieve a mobilisation of citizens for the protection and restoration of the Ocean". Source: https://oceandecade.org/events/the-ocean-science-to-art/	2024-2025	other	Centre of Marine Sciences of Algarve (CCMAR), Portugal
33	Art meets Science	"At the start of this year, a group of artists from the artist platform Wageningen (BKW) knocked on the door of the Science Shop with an intriguing question: what happens when Art meets Science?" Source: https://www.wur.nl/en/project/art-meets-science-science-shop.htm	2024-ongoing	other	Wageningen University & Research
34	Blue Genes - Collaborative Puzzle	"The aim of this project is to propose a cultural activity combining oceanographic science with various artistic practices. The objective is to help raise awareness of the ocean's climate challenges and the need to safeguard them". Source: https://www.ladisladsdesign.com/portfolio/giant-collaborative-puzzle-activity-blue-genes/	n/a	other	n/a

35	PROTECT BALTIC: Enabling comprehensive effective and efficient protection and restoration measures for a resilient Baltic Sea ecosystem	"A new approach to safeguard Baltic Sea biodiversity. In a race against time, the Baltic Sea region faces the challenge of doubling its marine protected areas to meet the EU Biodiversity Strategy's ambitious target. With 30 years spent achieving coverage of between 14 % and 17 %, and with almost non-existent strict protection, the clock is ticking to reach 30 % in just 8 years. With this in mind, the EU-funded PROTECT BALTIC project aims to strategically enhance the existing network. This transboundary initiative will establish an unparalleled data-driven evidence base, a regionally agreed protection framework, and concrete support to bridge gaps in protection and restoration efforts. PROTECT BALTIC is set to redefine marine protection in the Baltic Sea, ensuring a sustainable future for its unique biodiversity". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112866	2023-2028	MO	THE BALTIC MARINE ENVIRONMENT PROTECTION COMMISSION, Finland
36	DANUBE4all: RESTORATION OF THE DANUBE RIVER BASIN WATERS FOR ECOSYSTEMS AND PEOPLE FROM MOUNTAINS TO COAST	"Citizen engagement for river restoration. Europe's rivers are congested. More than a million barriers, like dams, ramps and fords, are causing extensive loss of river connectivity. In addition, human interventions have ecologically degraded a whopping 70 to 90 % of Europe's floodplain. Despite ambitious EU policy to turn things around, fresh and transitional water ecosystem restoration remains limited. The EU-funded DANUBE4all project will develop a comprehensive restoration action plan for the Danube River basin lighthouse. The project will engage stakeholders, integrating citizens' interests to support the EU Mission 'Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030' in an unprecedented cocreation process. The action plan will rely on solid scientific knowledge and new findings to promote ecological status, biodiversity, and ecosystem connectivity improvement". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093985	2023-2027	MO	UNIVERSITÄT FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
37	DTO-BioFlow: Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean	"AI-powered biodiversity data integration into the Digital Twin Ocean. The Horizon Europe Mission's objective is to safeguard the ocean and its biodiversity by 2030. To achieve this goal, the EU plans to establish a digital knowledge system, including a Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), which relies on accurate data regarding marine life and environmental pressures. The collection of this data is vital to ensure that the DTO effectively informs evidence-based policies. The EU-funded DTO-BioFlow project is dedicated to facilitating access to previously unused marine biodiversity data. It also aims to support the sustainable integration of both existing and new data from various sources. The project encompasses the development of the biological aspects of the DTO, encompassing data flows, models and algorithms". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112823	2023-2027	MO	VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR DE ZEE, Belgium
38	EFFECTIVE: Enhancing social well-being and economic prosperity by reinforcing the effectiveness of protection and restoration management in Mediterranean MPAs	"Digital protection and restoration management in the Mediterranean. Nature-based solutions (NBS) and digitalisation can help facilitate protection and restoration efforts. The EU-funded EFFECTIVE project is dedicated to establishing a comprehensive scientific knowledge base and providing guidance for the application of ecosystem-based management (EBM) to rehabilitate the EU's Mediterranean Blue Natural Capital. This involves scientific research, technology, NBS, digitalisation and considerations of social implications. The project aims to implement EBM in four pilot areas: Mar de l'Empordà, Ebro Delta, Sardinia Septentrional, and Cavo Greco. It aims to create an ecological corridor in the Mediterranean Sea, assess marine protected areas, showcase the use of NBS for seabed protection, address existing gaps in legislation, and introduce a digital tool for data exploration and citizen science participation". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112752	2023-2027	MO	ASOCIACION CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO NAVAL Y DEL MAR, Spain
39	DaWetRest: Danube Wetlands and flood plains Restoration through systemic, community engaged and sustainable innovative actions	"Creating a transformation in the Danube ecosystem. The Danube River, one of Europe's natural treasures, has been facing critical challenges in its inland and coastal wetlands ecosystems. With this in mind, the EU-funded DaWetRest Lighthouse project aims to develop and pilot innovative solutions that will transform the Danube basin. It will focus on biodiversity, water quality, climate resilience, and socio-economic benefits for local communities. These solutions will be rigorously validated by local communities and regional stakeholders. The project also seeks to lay the groundwork for the replication and scaling up of these solutions. To achieve this, DaWetRest will build on prior knowledge, integrating results from interventions at various scales, merging data and digital tools, and involving local authorities and actors from the outset". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101113015	2023-2027	MO	INSTITUT ZA IZSLEDVANIA HA KLIMATA, ATMOSFERATA I VODITE PRI BAN, Bulgaria
40	Restore4Life: Restoration of wetland complexes as life supporting systems in the Danube Basin	"Benefits of Danube basin freshwater and wetlands restoration. More than 70 % of the wetlands in the Danube Basin have been lost, and the remaining wetlands are under threat from human activity. In this context, the EU-funded Restore4Life project highlights the numerous socio-economic benefits of taking a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach to restoring freshwater and coastal wetlands in the Danube Basin. This initiative aims to facilitate the development of new blue-green infrastructure, enhancing the region's resilience to climate change and its impact. Restore4Life will carry out demonstrations at four sites and monitor six sites in the Danube Basin to showcase the advantages of improved delivery of essential ecosystem services such as water and pollutant retention, carbon sequestration and tourism opportunities". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112736	2023-2027	MO	UNIVERSITATEA DIN BUCURESTI, Romania

41	AlgaePro BANOS: Accelerating algae product developments in Baltic and North Sea	"Sustainable algae solutions for a thriving industry. The Baltic and North Sea (BANOS) area faces a critical challenge: reconciling economic development with social and environmental objectives in line with Mission Ocean. There is a rising demand for green and sustainable consumer products. In this context, the EU-funded AlgaePro BANOS project emerges as a pioneering solution. It aims to accelerate the development of and market access to algae-based solutions. Through six business pilots, the project will introduce eight algae products, ranging from food to cosmetics, fostering a sustainable industry that preserves precious resources while meeting consumer demands. The project's impact will extend beyond BANOS, benefiting the entire algae industry and contributing to a thriving future by 2050". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112943	2023-2027	MO	SUBMARINER NETWORK FOR BLUE GROWTH EWIV, Germany
42	LOCALITY: Nature-positive aLgae-based fOod, agriCulture, Aquaculture and textile products made in North and Baltic Sea ecosYstems	"Creating innovative value chains for algae-based products. In light of the impact of climate change and the significant damage caused by recent climate disasters, the EU is actively promoting the establishment of value chains across European industries and among various stakeholders. The algae industry presents a promising solution for fostering productive value chains through collaboration with other parties. The EU-funded LOCALITY project aims to create multiple innovative, local, and sustainable algae value chains in countries bordering the Baltic and North Seas. These chains will emphasise the potential synergies between actors in the algae industry and relevant waste stream producing sectors. The produced algae biomass will be used in sustainable product development, meeting different market sectors – food, aquafeed, agriculture, and textile". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112884	2023-2027	MO	NORSK INSTITUTT FOR VANNFORSKNING, Norway
43	INSPIRE: Innovative Solutions for Plastic Free European Rivers	"A holistic solution to safeguard the future of our rivers. European rivers are under siege, drowning in litter, macroplastics and microplastics. A threat to aquatic ecosystems, these pollutants compromise the very lifeforce of our continents. In this context, the EU-funded INSPIRE project brings together 20 groundbreaking technologies and strategic actions to detect, collect and prevent the proliferation of pollutants. It presents a holistic solution to safeguard the future of our rivers. These innovations will be tested through 6 use cases, with 26 partners across academia, industry and communication. INSPIRE charts a course towards cleaner rivers, setting a new standard for environmental stewardship". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112879	2023-2027	MO	VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR DE ZEE, Belgium
44	UPSTREAM: Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the Ultimate Prevention of Plastics in Rivers Integrated with Elimination And Monitoring Technologies	"Innovative solutions to deal with plastics in European rivers. The increasing presence of litter, plastics, and microplastics is causing further deterioration of European rivers. Consequently, it is necessary to develop new methods to control, prevent, and eliminate this pollution. The EU-funded UPSTREAM project is dedicated to addressing the challenges associated with monitoring, preventing, eliminating, and recycling litter, plastics, and microplastics. The project will showcase 14 solutions implemented at five European demonstration sites. These sites include four wastewater treatment plants connected to seven rivers in five countries, as well as a testing area on the Danube in Serbia. Additionally, the project will facilitate the creation of an extensive database of knowledge and sustainable business models, with a focus on ensuring wide accessibility to this information. Replication across Europe will be enhanced by EUR 300k allocated in cascade funding". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112877	2023-2027	MO	FUNDACION AITIIP, Spain
45	SeaClear2.0: Scalable Full-cycle Marine Litter Remediation in the Mediterranean: Robotic and Participatory Solutions	"Robotics and citizen engagement to tackle marine litter Robotics and citizen engagement can play a crucial role in achieving the EU Mission for ocean, seas and water health restoration by 2030. In this context, the EU-funded SeaClear2.0 project will develop an integrated approach to address the entire cycle of marine litter. The project will focus on reducing marine litter pollution, specifically from plastic litter, in the Mediterranean. This will be achieved by using teams of autonomous, intelligent robots to monitor and collect marine seafloor and surface litter, and through participatory practices to identify site-specific measures for marine litter prevention and reduction. By identifying ways to valorise litter and extend policy-making, SeaClear2.0 will provide innovative solutions for effective marine litter management, further promoting the health of oceans, seas, and water bodies". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093822	2023-2026	MO	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT, The Netherlands
46	BLUE4ALL: Blueprint demonstration for co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAs	"Networking to promote and protect marine ecosystems Marine protected areas (MPAs) are crucial in efforts to stem the loss of biodiversity and disruption of ocean ecosystems. MPAs are places in the ocean that receive protection to safeguard biodiversity from abatable threats. In this context, the EU-funded BLUE4ALL project will align top-down regulatory demands about European (networks of) MPAs with bottom-up societal expectations as a guarantee for achieving efficient and resilient MPAs and networks of MPAs which meet EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 objectives. The project will mobilise stakeholders from 25 information sites and living labs located across the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic Sea and the North-East Atlantic regions. The aim will be to promote knowledge transfer and cocreate robust and replicable social, governance, ecological and environmental tools". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094014	2023-2026	MO	INSTITUT ROYAL DES SCIENCES NATURELLES DE BELGIQUE, Belgium

47	OCEAN CITIZEN: Marine forest coastal restoration: an underwater gardening socio-ecological plan	"Advancing active restoration to promote coastal and offshore resilience. The loss and degradation of European marine ecosystems is alarming, especially those dominated by marine forests (seagrasses, seaweeds, sponge grounds, coral and gorgonian forests, etc.). There is an urgent need to prevent, stop and reverse this degradation. Active restoration has emerged as a preferred tool to boost marine-protected areas, also connecting healthy habitats. Not only does restoration promote biodiversity, but it also enhances carbon sequestration and boosts coastal and offshore resilience. In this context, the EU-funded OCEAN CITIZEN project will develop a new approach in which restoration serves as a toolbox holding ubiquitous properties. For instance, a profession of "gardeners of the sea" will be created and endorsed, intended to recover the most neglected marine biomes, marine forests". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093910	2023-2026	MO	UNIVERSITA DEL SALENTO, Italy
48	DALIA: Danube Region Water Lighthouse Action	"Policy tools to clean up the Danube River Home to nearly 80 million people, the Danube River Basin stretches across 19 European countries. Unfortunately, its main artery, the Danube River, is heavily affected by pollution. In this context, the EU-funded DALIA project will bring together 22 expert organisations from eight EU and associated countries to properly manage this complex and fragile ecosystem. The project will provide an integrated tool for better decision-making and improved restoration of fresh and transitional water ecosystems in the Danube River Basin. DALIA will contribute to the EU Water Framework Directive. It will also collaborate with a wider network of ecosystems and related EU Missions and projects". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094070	2023-2026	MO	ORSZAGOS VIZUGYI FOIGAZGATOSAG, Hungary
49	OLAMUR: Offshore Low-trophic Aquaculture in Multi-Use Scenario Realisation	"Growing seaweed and blue mussels within windfarms. As Europe's offshore renewables sector grows, so does the potential of low trophic aquaculture (LTA) for increasing seafood production. With this in mind, the EU-funded OLAMUR project will bring together key sectors to demonstrate sustainable commercial solutions for both the North and the Baltic Sea. It will establish three pilot demonstration sites where seaweed and blue mussels will be grown within windfarms or in the vicinity of a trout farm. A pilot site will be created off the coast of Germany's Helgoland island, another in the Baltic Sea at Kriegers Flak on the east coast of Denmark, and a third one off the coast of Estonia near the port of Veere". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094065	2023-2026	MO	HAVFORSKNINGSINSTITUTTE T, Norway
50	ULTFARMS: circUlar Low Trophic offshore Aquaculture in wind farms and Restoration of Marine Space	"Low trophic aquaculture in North and Baltic Sea offshore wind farms. The EU-funded ULTFARMS project aims to move beyond the current low trophic aquaculture (LTA) systems with novel engineering, technical, ecological and biological processes to improve production potential in harsh offshore conditions and/or low-salinities while supporting LTA integration with offshore wind farms (OWFs). The project will engage research and industry in co-developing and co-managing novel designs and operations in six LTA pilots in OWF locations across the North and Baltic Seas. The ambition is to advance LTA in offshore hostile environments while safeguarding the environment, minimising carbon footprint and addressing commercial viability. Finally, ULTFARMS will aim towards the replicability and transferability of the newly acquired knowledge". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093888	2023-2026	MO	STICHTING DELTARES, The Netherlands
51	ProBleu: Promoting ocean and water literacy in school communities	"Diving into ocean education. The world's oceans and freshwater bodies are threatened by pollution, ecosystem degradation and waning biodiversity. Urgent action is required to ensure the survival of these vital resources. In this context, the EU-funded ProBleu project aims to address the gaps in environmental education, foster a sense of responsibility towards water bodies and inspire behavioural change. As part of the Network of European Blue Schools, ProBleu sets out to make waves in the realm of ocean and water literacy. Specifically, it will introduce innovative resources grounded in open schooling methods. Not confined within classroom walls, the project fosters connections between communities and their local waters. It empowers students to contribute meaningfully to ocean and water literacy". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101113001	2023-2026	MO	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain
52	SHORE: EmpOwer Students as the agents of cHangE	"A rising tide against ocean illiteracy in Europe. As our oceans face unprecedented threats from climate change and pollution, the need for ocean literacy becomes increasingly evident. Across Europe, students and educators lack essential knowledge about marine ecosystems and sustainable practices. With this in mind, the EU-funded SHORE project aims to engage students, teachers and schools in the Baltic, Black and Mediterranean seas, and Danube and Rhine River areas. With 14 consortium partners, SHORE will increase awareness through community activities, workshops and exhibitions. A digital platform will track progress, while an annual public voting session will celebrate outstanding achievements, culminating in the prestigious Ocean Ambassador/Literate of the Year Award". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112815	2023-2026	MO	YILDIZ TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY, Türkiye

53	COOL BLUE: Community Ocean farms and Local Business cLUstErs	<p>"A sustainable seafood solution. As climate change intensifies, coastal and terrestrial fishing communities in Europe face severe challenges. While progress on climate action at the national level remains sluggish, local initiatives are stepping up to address the crisis. The EU-funded COOL BLUE project aims to empower communities to self-organise and embrace sustainable seafood practices. Not only will this initiative rejuvenate ecosystems but it will also foster community cohesion, creating resilient, self-sufficient socioecological systems. COOL BLUE's vision extends across Northern Europe, encompassing the Baltic and North Sea basins, uniting regions and initiatives to accelerate the development of low-impact ocean farming systems. Together, they strive to achieve the Mission Work Programme's goal of ocean and water recovery by 2030". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112747</p>	2023-2026	MO	S.PRO - SUSTAINABLE PROJECTS GMBH, Germany
54	SEARCULAR: Circular solutions for fishing gears	<p>"Four solutions to eliminate fishing waste. Our oceans are drowning in marine litter and microplastics, a crisis exacerbated by fishery contributors like demersal trawlers, demersal seiners, and tropical tuna purse seiners. As these industries persist with traditional non-circular plastic fishing gear, our waters suffer, and ecosystems pay the price. With this in mind, the EU-funded SEARCULAR project will develop and test four sustainable and circular solutions. The first involves dolly ropes made from recycled polyamide (rPA), sourced from discarded fishing nets. The second incorporates certified marine-biodegradable materials for demersal seine ropes. The third presents eco-designed biodegradable drifting fish aggregating devices, designed for tropical tuna purse seine fisheries. The fourth proposes an innovative end-of-life fishing gear management system in ports". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112852</p>	2023-2026	MO	FUNDACION AZTI - AZTI FUNDAZIOA, Spain
55	NETTAGPlus: Preventing, avoiding and mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter	<p>"Innovative approach to reducing the environmental impact of fishing. Fishing gear poses a threat to our seas, and fisheries activities lead to the generation of marine litter. The EU-funded NETTAGPlus project will develop three innovative and sustainable solutions to mitigate the adverse impacts of fishing gear on marine life and habitats. These solutions aim to prevent marine litter, minimise fishing gear loss, and remove abandoned fishing gear. By reducing abandoned, lost, and discarded fishing gear (ALDFG) and decreasing marine pollution, the project aims to minimise the introduction of hazardous chemicals and microplastics, and prevent ghost fishing and the entanglement of endangered species. Moreover, it will enhance the mapping, tracking, and retrieval of ALDFG technologies. NETTAGPlus will test these solutions in real conditions within Atlantic and Mediterranean countries". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112812</p>	2023-2026	MO	CENTRO INTERDISCIPLINAR DE INVESTIGACAO MARINHA E AMBIENTAL, Portugal
56	iMERMAID: Innovative solutions for Mediterranean Ecosystem Remediation via Monitoring and decontamination from Chemical Pollution	<p>"For a pollution-free Mediterranean Sea. The Mediterranean Sea faces a pressing challenge: chemical contamination and build-up. With anthropogenic influence surging since the industrial revolution, this pristine waterway is now vulnerable to emerging concerns. With this in mind, the EU-funded iMERMAID project will integrate, coordinate and synergise innovative solutions that prevent, monitor and remediate chemical contaminants. It will construct a multidimensional framework, underpinning policymaking and altering societal perspectives. Cutting-edge sensors and remediation methods will be advanced, tackling contaminants at their source while curbing upstream pollution. By bringing together SMEs, researchers, regulators and innovation professionals, iMERMAID aims to strengthen regulations, boost economic prospects, enhance EU residents' quality of life and, ultimately, create contaminant-free waters in the Mediterranean". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112824</p>	2023-2026	MO	FUNDACION INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN, Spain
57	RHE-MEDiation: Responsive hub for long term governance to destress the Mediterranean Sea from chemical pollution	<p>"De-stressing the Mediterranean by reducing pollution. The Mediterranean Sea holds immense environmental significance, impacting numerous countries, vast populations, as well as the fauna, flora, temperatures, and climates of the region. Its preservation and the mitigation of pollution within it, particularly in identified hotspots, are imperative elements of our battle against climate change. This urgency has propelled a heightened interest in devising solutions to curtail heavy metal, pesticide, PFAs, and perpetual chemical pollution in both freshwater and wastewater systems before they reach the sea. With this in mind, the EU-funded RHE-MEDiation project will support policymakers in enhancing governance practices. Furthermore, the project seeks to establish a pivotal centre for managing and monitoring endeavours related to pollution". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101113045</p>	2023-2026	MO	RINA CONSULTING SPA, Italy
58	eDNAqua-plan: A Plan towards an eDNA reference library and data repository for Aquatic Organisms, navigating Europe towards the next generation biodiversity monitoring	<p>"eDNA-based approach for the EU Mission Ocean strategy. The EU has set a goal to restore oceans and waters by 2030. Environmental DNA (eDNA) analysis can play a crucial role in achieving this objective. However, the implementation of eDNA-based methods faces challenges due to incomplete and disconnected reference libraries, as well as a lack of harmonised metadata. The EU-funded eDNAqua-plan project aligns with the EU Mission Ocean strategy. It focuses on gathering information about aquatic monitoring projects, initiatives, and infrastructures. The project will assess the feasibility of establishing a digital ecosystem of eDNA repositories and a reference library of marine and freshwater species. The goal is to support aquatic biodiversity monitoring programmes and develop a standardised approach for aquatic monitoring using eDNA tools". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112800</p>	2023-2026	MO	EUROPEAN MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRE EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM, France

59	ART4SEA - Melting Art, Creativity and Marine Sciences to foster Ocean Literacy in the Mediterranean area	"ART4SEA aims to create a transnational and interdisciplinary cooperation program that involves artists, creative professionals, digital media experts, and marine scientists to co-produce a combination of physical and digital artworks focused on raising the public awareness about Ocean Degradation and Climate Change, thus motivating people to assume a more environmentally friendly behaviour in their everyday life. ART4SEA will engage 24 international artists, selected through an open call, that will be trained by the project staff about: a) the main environmental challenges that marine scientists are facing; b) Ocean Literacy methods; c) sustainable practices in arts; d) digital technologies such as Virtual, Augmented and Mixed Reality". Source: https://culture.ec.europa.eu/creative-europe/projects/search	2023-2026	Creative Europe Programme	3D RESEARCH SRL, Italy
60	YDERST EUROPE - Facing the sea. A portrait of the European coast.	"Yderst Europe (YE) is an international photojournalistic project which promotes slow journalism and advocates space in the media for quiet knowledge and voices from native communities, coastal areas and communities in close correlation with nature. We also investigate Europe's transactions with the ocean". Source: https://culture.ec.europa.eu/creative-europe/projects/search	2023-2026	Creative Europe Programme	VESTERALEN REGIONRAD, Norway
61	ANERIS: operAtional seNsing life technologies for maRine ecosystemS	"New tools and methods to explore the ocean environment. Scientific and technological advances have increased our ability to observe the ocean environment. The EU-funded ANERIS project will develop cutting-edge scientific tools and methods for marine life sensing, integrating genomics, bio-optics, and participatory sciences. The project will involve numerous stakeholders in a codesign framework and introduce the concept of Operational Marine Biology as a biodiversity information system. The project will develop a training programme for all stakeholders and promote innovation and knowledge sharing among the academy, industry, governments, civil society, and research infrastructures. ANERIS will improve observational systems, providing new life-sensing technologies, empowering civil society, and integrating new-generation sensing instruments and methods". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094924	2023-2026	HORIZON	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain
62	BlueMissionAA: BUILDING A COORDINATION HUB TO SUPPORT THE MISSION IMPLEMENTATION IN THE ATLANTIC AND ARCTIC BASIN	"Region-specific ocean and waters restoration approaches. With a 2030 target, the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters' will protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research, innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments. The EU-funded BlueMissionAA will be the coordination hub that will support the implementation of the Mission in the Atlantic and Arctic basins. It will focus on the restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems and increased climate resilience. The project will mobilise a wide community of stakeholders and empower EU citizens to engage in preservation and restoration. It will also design a monitoring framework to assess progress. Six case studies will be selected across a range of restoration approaches, like active restoration and sustainable harvesting". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093962	2023-2025	MO	Atlantic International Research Centre (AIR Centre), Portugal
63	EDITO-Model Lab: Underlying models for the European Digital Twin Ocean - EDITO-Model Lab	"New tool to develop ocean management scenarios. In line with the Horizon Europe Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030', the development of a virtual ocean model lab (VOML) is underway. Bringing together ocean knowledge, modeling and technological expertise, the EU-funded EDITO-Model Lab project is designing next-generation ocean models as part of the European Digital Twin Ocean initiative. The aim is to enable stakeholders to develop ocean management scenarios. The project will deliver a VOML that will feature an interactive and codevelopment environment. The VOML will be based on modeling software, AI algorithms and special tools. The project will support the sustainable blue economy and explore 'what-if scenarios' to find solutions to natural and man-induced hazards". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093293	2023-2025	MO	MERCATOR OCEAN, France
64	OTTERS: Social Transformation for Water Stewardship through Scaling Up Citizen Science	"Citizen science initiatives for aquatic ecosystems sustainability. The EU Water Framework Directive promotes the protection of aquatic ecosystems and sustainable water use. Citizen science (CS) initiatives can contribute to and accelerate strategies' codesign and implementation. The EU-funded OTTERS project will encourage and scale up successful CS initiatives in the marine and freshwater domains. The project will accelerate the cocreation of standards in data collection, semantics, data quality, and data management in line with all ethical and legal standards and cluster them under codesigned Spring-to-Sea campaigns to foster agency and increase ocean literacy. The project will connect the citizen-generated data to other EU-funded projects and portals to ensure the accessibility and reuse of the data and will demonstrate the CS effectiveness". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094041	2023-2025	MO	AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION, Armenia

65	C-FAARER: Community-driven Farming for the Atlantic and Arctic sea basins through REgeneRative aquaculture	"A co-designed roadmap for regenerative ocean farming. To restore oceans and waters by 2030, sustainable business models for regenerative aquaculture, founded on science and collaboration with stakeholders, are essential. Ocean farmers must ensure that their practices are technically and economically viable. This approach should not only benefit ecosystem services, community resilience and job creation, but also tap into market potential. The EU-funded C-FAARER project aims to provide a co-designed roadmap and guidance to support ocean farmers in the Atlantic and Arctic Sea basins. The goal is to foster community-driven business models for regenerative ocean farming and enable policymakers to take appropriate actions. This project will analyse the impact of socio-economic and environmental factors on community business models in Norway and Ireland". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112729	2023-2025	MO	THE PROVOST, FELLOWS, FOUNDATION SCHOLARS & THE OTHER MEMBERS OF BOARD, OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY & UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN, Ireland
66	BoSS: Bauhaus of the Seas Sails	"Setting sail for climate neutrality. Oceans face numerous challenges, from plastic pollution to rising sea levels. It is possible to solve these environmental problems by mobilising cities close to water. This is the goal of the EU-funded BoSS project. Project work will result in transformational demonstrators across different regions and aquatic ecosystems in Portugal, Italy, Sweden, Germany, the Netherlands and Belgium. The overall aim is to achieve a sustainable and inclusive transition, keeping aesthetics at the centre and working with communities. The pilots will provide examples of mission-oriented approaches that are impactful and measurable. The project will introduce an ecocentric narrative both cosmopolitan and rooted in nature-based solutions". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079995	2023-2025	HORIZON	IST-ID ASSOCIACAO DO INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO PARA A INVESTIGACAO E O DESENVOLVIMENTO, Portugal
67	FLOW: Future Lives with Oceans and Waters	"Inviting Europe's young people to connect with the ocean. Covering more than two-thirds of Earth's surface, the ocean is essential to our survival. Restoring the health of our ocean and water is a top priority, in line with the European Green Deal goals. In this context, the EU-funded FLOW project will empower the young generation to co-create effective, target-group oriented and actionable blueprints for social interaction and engagement with our seas and waters. By bringing together a diverse group of young people from across Europe, FLOW will explore their expectations, engagements and human-nature relationship with the seas and waters. To achieve its goals, the project will design a new approach based on co-creating future policies that mitigate the risk of naively generalising and amplifying statements made by young people amid, and despite of, vested interests". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093928	2023-2024	MO	STICHTING RABBOUD UNIVERSITEIT, The Netherlands
68	BluePrint	"Ireland's climate is changing with impacts already being felt, and expected to continue and intensify, especially in coastal towns and cities, across Derry-Londonderry and Mayo, vulnerable to coastal and riverine floods. Floods and their catchments don't abide by administrative, geographical or political boundaries, as such knowledge exchange and learning between flood-affected communities and other government, scientific and policy actors is crucial. BluePrint addresses this need using a creative co-creation process in the Derry City and Strabane District area, an All-Island learning exchange with Mayo and a creative co-creation toolkit to support actors working with communities on climate adaptation and flood resilience across the island of Ireland". Source: https://www.marei.ie/project/blueprint/	2023-2024	other	Creative Climate Action Fund II – Agents for Change, an initiative from the Creative Ireland Programme
69	See Science, Save Seashores	"The project aims to better understand and protect the waterfront habitats of the Baltic Sea through innovations to the citizen science approach: networking, interdisciplinarity and accessibility of research. It will provide citizen research data about mesoplastic and seaweed distribution on Polish coastal lines, followed by their incorporation in environmental studies, carried out by scientists in the Institute of Oceanology of Polish Academy of Sciences in Sopot (IO PAN)". Source: https://impetus4cs.eu/see-science-save-seashores/	2023-2024	IMPETUS Accelerator grant	Institute of Oceanology of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IO PAS)
70	SHARED GREEN DEAL: SHARED GREEN DEAL: Social sciences & Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable GREEN DEAL	"The importance of society in driving solution for Europe's Green Deal. 22 leading organisations from across the EU have joined forces to explore the cross-cutting priorities of the European Green Deal. This includes topics such as democracy, energy and circular economy. Through the EU-funded SHARED GREEN DEAL project, the 22 partners will build a transnational network of policy stakeholders to shed light on the social and human factors necessary for achieving responsible and fair implementation of the European Green Deal. The project will incorporate lessons from six sets of social experiments on priority topics, each conducted across four Member States. Findings will address behavioural change, public trust and buy-in, and society's long-term commitment to the European Green Deal". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036640	2022-2027	HORIZON	ANGLIA RUSKIN UNIVERSITY HIGHER EDUCATION CORPORATION, United Kingdom
71	EcoDaLLI: ECOsystem-based governance with DANube lighthouse Living Lab for sustainable Innovation processes	'Innovative governance for the Danube basin restoration Delivering on the European Green Deal and the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030' requires integrated solutions and clear targets. The EU-funded EcoDaLLI project aims to centralise the governance structures of the Danube basin and its Delta through innovative solutions for ecological restoration, protection and preservation. The project will support the creation of an innovation ecosystem and a digital portal linked to the Mission Implementation Platform, delivering innovative solutions and tools for ecosystem services. This will contribute to the Green Deal goal of decarbonisation for cleaner water, improved environment, and job creation in sensitive areas". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093908	2022-2026	MO	STEINBEIS 21 GMBH, Germany

72	A-AAgora: Blueprint for Atlantic-Arctic Agora on cross-sectoral cooperation for restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems and increased climate resilience through transformative innovation	"Nature-based solutions to increase marine climate resilience. The EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" (Mission Ocean) aims to protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters. The EU-funded A-AAgora project will demonstrate via technological, social, logistic and economic innovation actions the reduction of pressures in coastal areas, through the application of ecosystem-based management and nature-based solutions to boost resilience to climate change and mitigate its impacts. A-AAgora will carry out demonstration activities in the Atlantic and Arctic basin and co-identify areas and locations where the solutions are replicable. Moreover, it will draw up blueprints and roadmaps to replicate and scale up the ecosystem and biodiversity restoration solutions and actions, contributing to Mission Ocean's development and the piloting phase of the Atlantic-Arctic basin lighthouse". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093956	2022-2026	MO	UNIVERSIDADE DE AVEIRO, Portugal
73	REMEDIES: Co-creating strong uptake of REMEDIES for the future of our oceans through deploying plastic litter valorisation and prevention pathways	"Innovative solutions for plastic litter valorisation and prevention. The EU-funded REMEDIES project aims to restore our seas and rivers through deploying (micro)plastic litter valorisation and prevention pathways. Project activities will revolve around monitoring and detection, collection and valorisation, and prevention and reuse of plastic waste. The REMEDIES movement is striving to co-create a plastic-conscious society by applying cutting-edge technology and circularity approaches, underpinned by a holistic citizen engagement framework. After validating the technologies in eight demonstration sites, they will be scaled up in 33 more locations across the Mediterranean, while 400 tonnes of plastic litter will be collected in the marine and riverine environment. Moreover, during this EU mission, EUR 500 000 of cascade funding will be granted to foster real zero-waste solutions with two open calls targeting five associated regions". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093964	2022-2026	MO	KEMIJSKI INSTITUT, Slovenia
74	SHiFT: CA21166 - Social Sciences and Humanities for Transformation and Climate Resilience	"SHiFT aims to address the challenge of generating innovative and actionable pathways by engaging with the 'critical practice' dimensions of transformation. A 'critical practice' approach explores transformation processes in practice across different dimensions which include research, policy, business, community and individual practices". Source: https://shift-cost.eu/	2022-2026	COST: European Cooperation in Science and Technology	CFE FCSH - NOVA University of Lisbon, Portugal
75	IMPETUS	"IMPETUS will support and give recognition to citizen science (CS) in Europe. It aims to: * enable more diverse citizen science initiatives (CSIs) to access funding; * bring CS closer to society and policy makers; * acknowledge CS? role in tackling the greatest challenges of our times; and * enable CSIs to contribute to Green Deal (GD) and UN SDG commitments". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058677	2022-2026	HORIZON	ZABALA INNOVATION CONSULTING SA, Spain
76	Sea2See: Innovative blockchain traceability technology and Stakeholders' Engagement strategy for boosting Sustainable Seafood visibility, social acceptance and consumption in Europe	"A novel blockchain technology for sustainable seafood transparency. Blockchain technologies can improve research methodology and transparency. In today's seafood traceability tools and services, blockchain technologies enable researchers to collect extensive data, making sustainable seafood practices more transparent to consumers. For the EU-funded Sea2See project, developing a novel end-to-end blockchain model and professional and consumer applications will fill in existing seafood traceability gaps. Trust and social acceptance of sustainably fished and farmed seafood will grow. Sea2See will do this by providing technological solutions that satisfy the need for data collection across the entire seafood value chain. It will target stakeholder and consumer engagement to introduce societal and sectoral strategies for increased creation, communication and awareness". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060564	2022-2026	HORIZON	SMARTWATER PLANET SL, Spain
77	SOS-ZEROPOL2030: Source to Seas - Zero Pollution 2030	"Taking a holistic approach to fight marine pollution. Curbing water pollution is a top priority in Europe. Keeping seas healthy and clean can help protect the various ecosystem services we depend on such as climate regulation and food provision. The EU-funded SOS-ZEROPOL2030 project seeks to make a significant contribution to this effort. To that end, it will develop a holistic framework aiming towards zero pollution in European seas by 2030. This framework will provide practical guidance from source to sea and address shortcomings in marine pollution management. Moreover, it will increase understanding of existing obstacles regarding prevention, reduction, mitigation and monitoring of marine pollution in European seas". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060213	2022-2026	HORIZON	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, Ireland
78	Marine SABRES: Marine Systems Approaches for Biodiversity Resilience and Ecosystem Sustainability	"Marine systems approaches for sustainable management. Social-ecological systems (SES) and ecosystem-based management (EBM) are globally recognised tools to enable balanced marine development and conservation. The EU-funded Marine SABRES project will co-design a simple SES approach to rapidly enable and upscale EBM across Europe and abroad. The project will set European marine management on a course to reverse biodiversity decline by integrating sustainable ecosystems and a resilient blue economy. Marine SABRES will empower managers to make sustainable decisions and citizens to engage with marine biodiversity conservation. The project will demonstrate the practical management efforts in the Tuscan Archipelago, the Arctic North-East Atlantic and the Macaronesian archipelagos". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058956	2022-2026	HORIZON	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, Ireland

79	ECS: European Citizen Science	"Building a European citizen science community. Growing a strong European citizen science community with access to open and FAIR data with open and FAIR tools is key for the EU-funded ECS project. It will carry out various activities including setting up a network of ECS ambassadors and a European citizen science academy to build capacity and raise awareness. ECS will leverage the EU-Citizen.Science platform and Cos4Cloud to facilitate cooperation between ECS community members, who in turn will play an instrumental role in the design and creation of policy, strategic priorities, services, and training activities. Opportunities for ensuring inclusion will be determined, as will activities to engage researchers from diverse disciplines. Ultimately, ECS will propel forward Europe's role in global research and innovation". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058509	2022-2026	HORIZON	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V., Germany
80	MIP Ocean: The Mission Ocean and Waters Implementation Platform	"The Mission Ocean and Waters Implementation Platform (MIP Ocean) serves as a platform in coordinating efforts under the EU Mission Ocean and Waters. This platform supports the European Commission's implementation by facilitating knowledge-sharing, communication and technical assistance across the Mission community. MIP Ocean monitors and evaluates progress in achieving mission objectives, provides tools for collaboration and drives regional and local engagement through initiatives such as the Mission Charter". Source: https://erin.eu/projects/mission-ocean-and-waters-implementation-platform#:~:text=The%20Mission%20Ocean%20and%20Waters%20Implementation%20Platform%20%28MIP,efforts%20under%20the%20EU%20Mission%20Ocean%20and%20Waters. / https://www.technopolis-group.com/new/the-launch-of-mission-restore-our-oceans-and-waters-by-2030-implementation-platform/	2022-2026	Other	Technopolis Group
81	BlueMissionMed: Lighthouse coordinating and supporting the innovation ecosystem for a Healthy, Pollution free Mediterranean Sea	"Supporting the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" In line with the European Green Deal, the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" aims to eliminate pollution and make the blue economy (the economic activities that depend on the sea) carbon-neutral and circular. In this context, the EU-funded BlueMissionMed project will inspire, inform, assess, mobilise, connect and empower all the actors that can take a role in preventing and eliminating pollution in the Mediterranean sea and waters. The project will build on, connect and structure existing initiatives and activities with the aim of designing and supporting a well-functioning basin scale innovation ecosystem as well as upscaling solutions in all forms (technological, social, business, governance). The aim is to ensure fast progress towards the achievement of the Mission objectives". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094073	2022-2025	MO	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy
82	CLIMAREST: Coastal Climate Resilience and Marine Restoration Tools for the Arctic Atlantic basin	"Improving climate resilience in EU coastal regions. Climate change is impacting coastal regions all along the European coastline, which is home to over 40 % of the continent's population. Therefore, ecosystem restoration and initiatives to enhance climate resilience in these regions are a top priority. In this context, the EU-funded CLIMAREST project will develop, test and optimise a modular toolbox that integrates expert knowledge, scientific information, multilevel stakeholder and community involvement, ecosystem service improvement analysis, cost-benefit analysis, priority of actions, and custom-designed protocols for restoring and monitoring a wide range of diverse coastal habitats. The toolbox framework will be tested in five ecosystems across a latitudinal gradient of the Arctic-Atlantic basin. The tools will be further tested for upscaling in comparable ecosystems". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093865	2022-2025	MO	SINTEF OCEAN AS, Norway
83	PlasticPiratesEU: UPSCALING THE PLASTIC PIRATES CITIZEN SCIENCE INITIATIVE	"Increasing awareness of plastic waste pollution in European waters. The citizen science initiative 'Plastic Pirates – Go Europe!' aims to raise awareness throughout Europe of the importance of rivers, the protection of natural resources, and the significance of international research collaboration. The EU-funded PlasticPiratesEU project will upscale 'Plastic Pirates – Go Europe!' in countries across Europe by raising awareness among citizens and the youth of Europe on the impact and benefits of research and innovation and increasing the capacity to collect, organise and verify data on plastic waste pollution stemming from and in European rivers, coastlines, and seas. The project will test, replicate and refine best practice models to achieve Mission Ocean's objective". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101088822	2022-2025	MO	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FÜR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV, Germany
84	EDITO-Infra: EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean	"Public access to open ocean observation data. Europe is building a full-fledged digital twin of the ocean (DTO) that will combine next generation ocean modelling, artificial intelligence and machine learning. By connecting high-performance computing and marine infrastructure, Copernicus satellites and underwater drones, the DTO will allow to monitor and enhance marine and coastal habitats. The EU-funded EDITO-Infra project will build the EU Public Infrastructure backbone for the DTO. It will upgrade, combine and integrate the key service components of the Copernicus Marine Service and the European Marine Observation and Data Network into a single digital framework. This will provide the foundation for the further development of Europe's DTO initiative and provide public access to the widest possible range of open ocean observation datasets". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101101473	2022-2025	MO	MERCATOR OCEAN, France

85	EmpowerUs: Socio-economic Empowerment of coastal communities as users of the sea to ensure sustainable coastal development	"Green transition through coastal communities. Coastal communities are significant to maintaining healthy climates and transitioning to a more sustainable, green and inclusive world. Unfortunately, in many cases, policies, funding and novel solutions do not take these communities into account, either making inefficient changes or forgetting them altogether. The EU-funded EmpowerUs project will develop a network of six transition coastal labs across EU coastal regions promoting new effective methodologies for inclusive policymaking. EmpowerUs will enhance social innovation and self-sustainability, allowing the optimisation of each community and pushing for a greener future". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059957	2022-2025	HORIZON	NORDLANDSFORSKNING AS, Norway
86	ILIAD: INTEGRATED Digital Framework FOR Comprehensive MARITIME DATA AND INFORMATION SERVICES	"A data-intensive, cost-effective Digital Twin of the Ocean. A digital twin of the ocean allows experts to develop what-if scenarios, analysing the impact of measures to prevent and adapt to climate change. Integrating various data sources is key to formulating predictions of future developments in marine social-ecological systems. The EU-funded ILIAD project creates an interoperable, data-intensive, and cost-effective Digital Twin of the Ocean contributing to the implementation of the European Green Deal. It capitalises on the increasing wealth of data and advanced computing infrastructures by combining these diverse data in a semantically rich and data-agnostic approach allowing simultaneous communication with real-world systems and models. ILIAD will also create a marketplace to distribute apps, plug-ins, interfaces, raw data, citizen science data, synthesised information and value-added services." Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101037643	2022-2025	HORIZON	NETCOMPANY - INTRASOFT, Belgium
87	CrossGov: Coherent and cross-compliant ocean governance for delivering the EU Green Deal for European Seas	"Enhancing policy and legislation to achieve Green Deal marine-related goals. The European Green Deal (GD) calls for a deep transformation of policies, including all those that affect the oceans. Responsibilities are dispersed over many levels of governance and many sectors. CrossGov will advance knowledge on how coherence and cross-compliance of marine-related policies and legislation impact efforts to realise relevant GD goals. Methods for evaluating coherence will be applied in studies of coherence of EU legislation and policy, and of national transposition. Case studies of cross-compliance will study the alignment of different directives affecting marine environments and of GD policy integration into sectoral policies. Policymakers and stakeholders will be closely involved, including in recommending improved governance, and in making an analytical toolbox that can be applied by researchers and end-users". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060958	2022-2025	HORIZON	NORSK INSTITUTT FOR VANNFORSKNING, Norway
88	DANUBIUS Implementation Phase Project - DANUBIUS-IP	"DANUBIUS-IP is a 36-month Coordination and Support Action to support the ongoing development of DANUBIUS-RI – an environmental research infrastructure linking rivers and seas – as it proceeds towards its Operational Phase. The project proposes 7 work packages, in two parallel workstreams, that together will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • deliver a new governance structure for the RI as it transitions to DANUBIUS-ERIC; • enhance the ICT potential of the RI to enable virtual delivery of key services; • implement the Science and Innovation Agenda supported by agile and quality assured scientific services; • demonstrate the value of the RI through examples of the unique services that the RI can offer to end-users across Europe and internationally; • expand the DANUBIUS-RI community and enhance its standing in the wider European and International environmental RI landscape; and • ensure that the potential of DANUBIUS-RI to have significant social and economic impact is widely communicated". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079778 	2022-2025	HORIZON	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU GEOLOGIE SI GEOECOLOGIE MARINA-GEOECOMAR, Romania
89	MarinePlan: Improved transdisciplinary science for effective ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning and conservation in European Seas	"Decision-support system for ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning. Every single plant and animal on Earth is a member of an ecosystem. The importance of ecosystem biodiversity cannot be underestimated, mainly because of climate change. The effective management of marine activities and the sustainable use of marine and coastal resources are top priorities. Maritime spatial planning (MSP) is the governance process responsible for achieving and maintaining the balance between maritime sustainability and exploitation. However, transboundary coordination and policymaking challenges make this difficult. The EU-funded MarinePlan project supports the implementation of ecosystem-based MSP through the development of a decision support platform. It will offer guidance for an improved alignment of MSP, spatial conservation and restoration measures during the challenging times of ever-increasing pressures on marine ecosystems". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059407	2022-2025	HORIZON	JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI, Germany

90	GUARDEN: safeGUARDing biodiversity and critical ecosystem services across sectors and scales	"A decision support tool for biodiversity protection. Healthy communities rely on well-functioning ecosystems. Global biodiversity preservation is a prerequisite for successful climate change mitigation and adaptation and the continued well-being of fauna, flora and all life. However, this is not easy. The EU-funded GUARDEN project will introduce a user oriented decision support application. It will create multistakeholder partnerships and collect data that can help organisations, stakeholders and policymakers make informed decisions. To increase the amount of geo-localised biodiversity data and build a new generation of predictive models of biodiversity and ecosystem status indicators, GUARDEN will make use of deep learning, Earth observation, and hybrid modeling". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060693	2022-2025	HORIZON	CENTRE DE COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE EN RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT - C.I.R.A.D. EPIC, France
91	OCEAN NIGHT: helping society understand the importance of the marine ecosystem	"Raising awareness of the importance of the marine ecosystem. Life started in the ocean more than 3.5 billion years ago. Nowadays oceans represent the largest ecosystem on Earth, covering more than 70% of its surface. Billions of humans live in coastal areas and rely on well-functioning marine ecosystems for their survival. Unfortunately, this great resource is being damaged by human activities, both direct, like overfishing, and indirect like global warming. The EU-funded OCEAN NIGHT project will raise awareness of this ecosystem's importance and the challenges it faces. The project will bring together all public research institutes across Spain working on marine science for a comprehensive two-year outreach programme of events aimed at engaging a geographically wide and socially diverse set of regions within the country". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101061165	2022-2024	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain
92	A touch of Blue in the EU Research Nights for a more Sustainable Use of the Ocean	"Oceans are vast, covering over 70 % of the Earth's surface. Growing knowledge about this continuous body of salt water and the people that study it is key. The EU-funded BlueNIGHTs project seeks to help citizens better understand the many facets and faces of those working in ocean science and research. A series of interconnected EU Blue Researchers' Nights will demonstrate that not only is the ocean interesting and a source of inspiration, but it is also a field of study for people with diverse backgrounds and interests. BlueNIGHTs will connect people to important objectives, principles and priorities of the European Green Deal that relates to the ocean, thereby encouraging Europeans to become more knowledgeable about the ocean..". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101061605	2022-2024	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy
93	PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters	"Co-creation and co-implementation of research for ocean and water health Research and innovation (R&I) will be a central component of the Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters, which aims to restore ocean and water health by 2030. The Mission will connect initiatives across disciplines, mobilise policymakers, stakeholders and citizens, and leverage public and private investments. The EU-funded PREP4BLUE project will develop tools and methods for co-creation and co-implementation of R&I modalities, which are required by the Mission objectives. It will also prepare the ground for stimulating and engaging various actors for a successful first phase (2022–2025). The project will deliver tools, guidelines, methodologies and recommendations tested through pilots, which will interconnect, leverage and optimise actions among the projects contributing to the Mission". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056957	2022 - 2025	MO	L'Institut Français de Recherche pour L'Exploitation de la Mer, France
94	CREAMARE: Linking creativity, culture and media technologies in the transnational co-production of digital interactive products for the communication of maritime and underwater cultural heritage	"Linking creativity, culture and media technologies in the transnational co-production of digital interactive products for the communication of maritime and underwater cultural heritage". Source: https://creamare.eu/ & https://culture.ec.europa.eu/creative-europe/projects/search/?page=1&sort=&domain=ce2021&view=list&map=false&keyword=CREAMARE	2022-2025	Creative Europe Programme	3D RESEARCH SRL, Italy
95	BlueMissionBANOS – supporting the Mission Ocean Lighthouse in the Baltic and North Sea basins	"Engaging stakeholders in EU Mission Ocean Lighthouse. The EU mission 'Restore our Ocean, Seas and Waters by 2030' will advance concrete solutions to protect the EU's ecosystems and biodiversity, prevent and eliminate pollution and make the blue economy carbon-neutral and circular. As the mission establishes lighthouse projects, 'Blue Parks', and improved digital knowledge systems, wider engagement of stakeholders is needed. The EU-funded BlueMissionBANOS project will act as a facilitator and knowledge broker to inspire, engage and support stakeholders in politics, industry and science across the Baltic and North Sea (BANOS) basins, to channel resources effectively towards the Mission Ocean objectives. The consortium includes active research institutes, networks/clusters and funding agencies and will work with regional and governance structures". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093845	2022 - 2025	MO	SUBMARINER NETWORK FOR BLUE GROWTH EWIV, Germany
96	The European Marine Board The EMBracing the Ocean programme	"EMB's artist-in-residence programme 'EMBracing the Ocean' provides grants for creative individuals or groups to co-create work with Ocean scientists. It aims to raise societal awareness of and embrace connection to the Ocean, inspire positive behaviour towards sustainability, and contribute new insights and/or perspectives to science". Source: https://www.marineboard.eu/emb-artist-residence-programme	2021-ongoing	other	European Marine Board, Belgium

97	ARTPORT_WE ARE OCEAN	"ARTPORT_WE ARE OCEAN is a transdisciplinary artistic project involving multiple stakeholders (artists, students, scientists, policy makers, teachers, curators, activists) worldwide to raise awareness and engage in dialogue about the environmental condition of the ocean and the role humans play in its current and future state. This effort started in 2019 and will engage with numerous countries until 2030 to work particularly with young and underprivileged around the question of how we interact with the ocean and how interdependent humans and the ocean are. The overall goal is to raise scientific and political awareness through the arts, particularly among young people. Source: https://oceandecade.org/actions/artport_we-are-ocean/	2021-2030	other	ARTPORT_making waves, Germany
98	WaterLANDS: Water-based solutions for carbon storage, people and wilderness	"(...) Applying a community-led paradigm in the co-design of restoration and empowering, engaging and reconnecting with nature". Source: https://waterlands.eu/project-overview/	2021-2026	HORIZON	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, Ireland
99	MINKE: Metrology for Integrated Marine Management and Knowledge-Transfer Network	"Innovative design to monitor and manage data on marine ecosystems. The EU-funded MINKE project will integrate key European marine metrology research infrastructures to propose an innovative framework of 'quality of oceanographic data' for European actors monitoring and managing marine ecosystems. MINKE proposes a new vision in the design of marine monitoring networks using two dimensions of data quality, accuracy and completeness, as the driving components of quality in data acquisition. This vision will be applied in a quintuple helix model of innovation, incorporating all elements involved in the monitoring network design. MINKE will lay the groundwork for creating the necessary synergies among different actors in the quintuple helix model of innovation, creating a new community with complementary capabilities for the ocean and coastal observation to facilitate the transition towards a blue growth socio-economic system". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101008724	2021-2025	HORIZON	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain
100	SATURN: Solutions @ Underwater Radiated Noise	"Multidisciplinary action to address impacts of underwater radiated noise. Underwater radiated noise (URN) emitted from commercial ships and other vessels can negatively impact aquatic species and their ecosystems, potentially threatening their survival. The EU-funded SATURN project brings together expertise from disciplines like bioacoustics, maritime engineering, shipping and other fields, to engage stakeholders to develop solutions to the problem of URN. SATURN will examine: i) which sounds pose the greatest threat to aquatic species and how they are produced and propagated; ii) short and long-term effects of URN on invertebrates, fish, and marine mammals; and iii) the most promising options for reducing negative impacts of URN. SATURN will develop and progress standards for terminology and methodology across all disciplines working on URN, producing recommendations for effective underwater sound management". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006443	2021-2025	HORIZON	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK, Ireland
101	DOORS: Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea	"Open doors' for research and innovation in the Black Sea. The Black Sea is a unique sea basin, rich in biodiversity, geological and cultural heritage, which is subject to combined effects of natural and human-induced stressors. The Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) coordinates stakeholders from academia, funding agencies, industry, policy and society to address the specific challenges of this marine basin and promote Blue Growth and economic prosperity in the region. The EU-funded DOORS project will implement the SRIA in close cooperation with stakeholders and other projects in the region. It will harmonise research, deliver the infrastructure required to understand the Black Sea ecosystems, develop a structure to support Blue Growth and the early development of start-ups, and provide evidence to shape policy in line with the Black Sea SRIA". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000518	2021-2025	HORIZON	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU GEOLOGIE SI GEOECOLOGIE MARINA-GEOECOMAR, Romania
102	YOUCCOUNT - EMPOWERING YOUTH AND COCREATING SOCIAL INNOVATIONS AND POLICYMAKING THROUGH YOUTH-FOCUSED CITIZEN SOCIAL SCIENCE	"Youth citizen social science key to the social inclusion of young people. Across Europe, many young people are at risk of being left out of society. The EU-funded YouCount project aims to explore how more inclusive and youth-friendly societies can be created. Through youth citizen social science (YCSS), young people aged between 15 and 29 will help the project's researchers investigate what creates social inclusion as well as co-create innovations and measures that can help promote social inclusion and belonging among young people. The project's work will also provide evidence on the outcomes of YCSS through citizen science activities". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101005931	2021-2024	HORIZON	OSLOMET - STORBYUNIVERSITETET, Norway

103	INCENTIVE: Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society	"Transforming research and societies with the aid of citizens. Citizen science is a broad term that encompasses that part of open science where citizens can participate in the scientific process in a variety of ways: by observing, analysing or producing data. Being pivotal to the democratisation of science, citizen science requires an adequate framework to function properly and to engage the public and stakeholders as much as possible. The EU-funded INCENTIVE project aims to support Europe's research performing and funding organisations (RPFOS) in establishing sustainable transdisciplinary hubs for stimulating and supporting excellent citizen science. Besides being a sustainable institutional change themselves, citizen science hubs will serve as a vehicle for introducing considerable institutional changes in European RPFOS and their communities". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101005330	2021-2024	HORIZON	UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE, The Netherlands
104	SensJus: Citizen Sensing as a source of evidence in environmental justice litigation and as a tool for environmental mediation	"Exploring citizen sensing as a source of evidence in litigation. A civic group, which involved volunteer observations performed over years, brought a clean water violation case, based in part on citizen-sensed evidence, to a Texas court in 2019. The evidence of this grassroots-driven environmental monitoring contributed to the verdict that a petrochemical company was responsible for violating the Clean Water Act. This is an example of citizen science and, more specifically, 'citizen sensing'. The EU-funded SensJus project will investigate the potential litigation and mediation role of citizen science in the EU. The key objective is to fill a knowledge gap as regards introducing citizen sensing as a source of evidence in litigation over environmental wrongdoings. The research will be hosted by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC)". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/891513	2021-2023	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Belgium
105	TIME4CS: Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology	"Sustainable institutional changes to promote public engagement in science and technology. Citizen science - the participation of citizens in scientific research to increase scientific knowledge - has experienced growth and increased popularity in recent years, enabling the democratisation of science. The EU-funded TIME4CS project aims at supporting and facilitating sustainable institutional changes in research organisations to promote public engagement (citizens and citizens associations) and citizen science in science and technology. Focussing on four intervention areas and key features of institutional change, the project will create a knowledge transfer and mutual learning programme which will lead to the development of tailored roadmaps". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006201	2021-2023	HORIZON	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA, Italy
106	Aqua Granda, a Digital Community Memory	"The Aqua Granda Community Memory is a living system, which allows anyone to access, augmented and (re)interpret its contents in relation to an ever-changing present. The basis is there but now it is in the hands of all those who care about Venice to further expand and use it as a tool to commemorate the Aqua Granda's events and to find a path towards the future livability and sustainability of this unique city. The project "Aqua Granda, a Digital Community Memory" has been launched on 12 November 2020 by the H2020 EU Odysseus project, Ca' Foscari University and Science Gallery di Venezia". Source: https://www.aquagrandainvenice.it/en/about	2020	HORIZON	Ca' Foscari University and Science Gallery di Venezia, Italy
107	Surfing for Science	"Vast amounts of microplastics have been found floating on the surface of subtropical oceanic gyres. However, the distribution of floating plastic in the ocean is still poorly constrained, and there is a lack of information from coastlines. The reason behind is the general use of trawls towed by research vessels to collect scientific samples. We have designed a net trawl to collect samples in the nearshore from SUPs, kayaks, and rowing boats". Source: https://ars.electronica.art/citizenscience/en/surfing-for-science/ and https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters/surfing-science-scientific-data#solution-details	2020	European Union Prize for Citizen Science – Honorary Mentions	The University of Barcelona and the Spanish delegation of Surfider Foundation
108	TPAAE: Transcultural Perspective in Art and Art Education	"Creating and teaching art in transcultural effort. Avant-garde African and European art have influenced each other. These impacts are worthy of more research as a common ground for studies and activities enables collaborations in the transcultural perspective. The EU-funded TPAAE project will study contemporary art in Africa and Europe as well as the forms of art education in both continents. Participant academic and art institutions from Italy, Kenya and Poland will conduct academic exchanges, theoretical studies and practical activities to share competences in the field of cultural heritage and art teaching. It will enable the Fine Arts and Design department at Pwani University have dialogue with European institutions and support the development of art in the Kilifi region (Kenya)". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872718	2020-2024	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	AKADEMIA SZTUKI W SZCZECINIE, Poland

109	NEWSERA: Citizen Science as the new paradigm for Science Communication	"Citizen science changing science communication. Citizen science (CS) offers an important service for both science and society. Success hinges on the participation of key stakeholders (interdisciplinary scientists, public sector, industry, CS organisations and society), which is indispensable. However, there is a wide range of specific science communication instruments and strategies available for every target group, and constant feedback for each stakeholder group is required. The EU-funded NEWSERA project will analyse and evaluate the complex science communication strategies directed at the stakeholders in CS programmes all over Europe, creating a new paradigm in science communication. Four pilot case studies will be conducted under the new platform, taking into consideration the quality, quantity and reliability of science communication". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/873125	2020-2023	HORIZON	SCIENCE FOR CHANGE, SL, Spain
110	AMASS: Acting on the Margins: Arts as Social Sculpture	"The arts: A social sculpture. The arts can move people, educate societies and question widely accepted narratives. The arts can also shed new light on the past, hold up a mirror to contemporary life and launch new perspectives for the future. AMASS, an arts-based action research project, aims to create concrete opportunities for people to come together and accompany artists as agents in creative projects and interpretations. This multidisciplinary project will consider a wide field of disciplines and through participatory approaches, it will use practical methods from the field of service design to explore the role of the arts in mitigating societal challenges, aiming at capturing, assessing and harnessing the societal impact of the arts and further generate social impact through policy recommendations. It will also identify, explore, collate, evaluate and analyse existing and new innovative productions, experiments and case studies from the perspective and the physical positioning of European countries 'on the margins' in the underserved northern, southern, western and eastern regions". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/870621	2020-2023	HORIZON	LAPIN YLIOPISTO, Finland
111	CoAct: Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action	"How vulnerable citizens can serve as co-researchers. Research into the field of citizen social science remains rather limited. Nevertheless, citizen groups emerge as co-researchers and co-designers in many research and innovation activities. The EU-funded CoAct project proposes a fundamentally new approach to tackling social global concerns related to mental health care, youth employment, environmental justice and gender equality: by engaging vulnerable citizens acting as co-researchers. The project will run in Barcelona, Vienna, Berlin and eastern Europe, as well as Buenos Aires. It will be implemented by a consortium of research institutions, NGOs and global networks of open science and open data activism. The project's goal is identify and develop a general model for citizen social science that engages citizen bodies concerned with specific social issues in co-research". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/873048	2020-2022	HORIZON	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA, Spain
112	OptimCS: Optimising big data from citizen science projects for biodiversity research	"Making the most of citizen science in nature. Citizen science is a broad term used to describe the general public's engagement in scientific research activities. It spans a range of levels of engagement: from being better informed about science to participating in the scientific process (observing, gathering or processing data). Citizen science can be particularly valuable for society, ecology and conservation. The EU-funded OptimCS project will build a workflow to maximise the information that citizen scientists contribute to our collective knowledge of biodiversity. The data collection power of citizen science is enormous, but as citizen science at this scale is a new development in ecology and conservation, there is a great deal of inefficiency in this process". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/891052	2020-2022	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	MARTIN-LUTHER-UNIVERSITÄT HALLE-WITTENBERG, Germany
113	There is Sea and Sea... there is an Entire Ocean to Take Care of	"The aim of the project "There is Sea and Sea... there is an Entire Ocean to Take Care of", with the acronym OceanCare (2020-2022), is to raise awareness of human influence on the oceans. They allow to verify the effects of plastic on the ocean in loco and delineate/develop actions that aim to minimize this impact, involving the local community, encouraging them to change habits and behaviors. By encouraging fieldwork in coastal areas, this project meets the new trends in education, which favor the teaching of transversal themes, through experiences inside and outside the classroom". Source: https://sakalaera.ee/en/erasmus-projects/ and https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/projects/search/details/2020-1-PT01-KA229-078877	2020-2022	ERASMUS+	Agrupamento de Escolas Moinhos da Arroja, Portugal
114	EU-Citizen.Science: The Platform for Sharing, Initiating, and Learning Citizen Science in Europe	"Innovation for European citizen science. The rise of citizen science as a domain of innovation is hindered by its heterogeneity, which leads to a European citizen science environment that is fragmented and not fully coordinated. The EU-funded EU-Citizen.Science project will build and advance a sustainable platform and mutual learning space supplying different tools, best practice examples and relevant scientific results. The innovation targets three interlinked activities: coordination of citizen science actions and support of existing resources in the fragmented European citizen science environment; gaining the commitment of quadruple helix stakeholders at local, national and European levels; and creation of a mutual learning space. The project will advance interdisciplinary, cross-border and cross-sector collaboration and encourage social innovation and new business models". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824580	2019-2021	HORIZON	MUSEUM FÜR NATURKUNDE - LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FÜR EVOLUTIONS- UND BIODIVERSITÄTSFORSCHUNG AN DER HUMBOLDT-UNIVERSITÄT ZU BERLIN, Germany

115	StART: Science through ART	<p>"Interactions between art and science in Ankara. The EU-funded StART project will organise Researchers' Night 2019 in Turkey to promote public awareness of 'Science through ART – StART' through events around five key areas. Each area corresponds to a branch of art: drawing painting, sculpture, architecture, music-dance and photography. The Science and Society Center of Middle East Technical University (ODTÜ) in Ankara will perform activities involving science and art communicators to explain through their work the many interactions between science and art, showing the potential of mutual inspiration and collaboration between art and science. The project will also focus on children, from pre-schoolers to secondary school students, to encourage them to embark on a scientific career". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818781</p>	2019-2019	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY, Türkiye
116	Embassy of the North Sea	<p>"Diversity is in the interest of all life. Therefore, direct political representation of the sea and the life within it is necessary. The Embassy of the North Sea was founded on the principle that the North Sea owns itself. Our aim is to represent the plants, animals, microbes, and people in and around the North Sea in the cultural, legal and political public domain. We have plotted a route through to 2030, firstly learning to listen to the sea before we learn to speak with it. Finally, we will negotiate on behalf of the North Sea and all the life that it encapsulates". Source: https://www.embassyofthenorthsea.com/</p>	2018-ongoing	other	Embassy of the North Sea
117	NextGen: Towards a next generation of water systems and services for the circular economy.	<p>"The NextGen initiative will evaluate and champion innovative and transformational circular economy solutions and systems that challenge embedded thinking and practices around resource use in the water sector. We will produce new understandings to underpin the exploitation of techniques and technologies that enhance our ability to recover, refine, reuse, repurpose, capture value from, and extend the use-life of, an ever-increasing range of resources and products, thereby projecting the European water and allied sectors as global circular economy pioneers. NextGen will demonstrate innovative technological, business and governance solutions for water in the circular economy in ten high-profile, large-scale, demonstration cases across Europe, and we will develop the necessary approaches, tools and partnerships, to transfer and upscale". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776541</p>	2018-2022	HORIZON	KWR WATER BV, The Netherlands
118	Sunken Spectre	<p>"Sunken Spectre is an stealth / deep sea diving adventure with missions set in a variety of locations around the globe, both on land and beneath the waves. Set in the late 1970s, players take on the role of Jac Moore, captain of a small deep sea recovery vessel. After turning her back on a life of crime, and her former employer Royale LeStrange, Jac purchased an old scuttled boat called The Spectre. With the help of her friend, Strong, she repaired the boat and made it sea worthy again. Jac gathered her own rag-tag crew, formed her own diving operation and now dives for clients all over the globe. For the right price the crew of the spectre will retrieve whatever you need from the bottom of the ocean. No job is to far, too deep or too dangerous. They quickly discover that in this line of work you can quite literally get in over your head. The missions they pursue are mired by sharks, strange supernatural occurrences, bizarre legendary creatures, and of course Jac's old boss and main competitor, Royale LeStrange. The series of five adventures include an investigation into a yacht sank by mystical creatures off the coast of Miami, an ancient Greek goddess imprisoned at the bottom of the Mediterranean, a hallucinogenic chemical weapon leaking into the ocean, a mysterious pyramid beneath the waves, and a long lost ship still manned by a literal skeleton crew. Only by working together and using their wits can Jac and her ragtag crew of misfits succeed on the extraordinary adventures that await them". Source: https://culture.ec.europa.eu/creative-europe/projects/search/details/602626-CREA-1-2018-1-IE-MED-DEVVG</p>	2018-2021	Creative Europe Programme	ISOMETRIC DREAMS LIMITED, Ireland
119	InSPIRES: Ingenious Science shops to promote Participatory Innovation, Research and Equity in Science.	<p>"Ingenious science shops for participatory innovation, research and equity in science. The EU-funded InSPIRES project will assemble practitioners and experts from Europe and beyond to co-design, pilot and implement innovative models for Science Shops (SS). It will integrate responsible research and innovation (RRI), open science and impact evaluation into its models, enabling the sustainable dissemination of research processes to civil society. Targeting research and innovation in the health sector, while focusing on gender parity and vulnerable groups, InSPIRES will organise public engagement initiatives with a 'glocal' international scope. Outcomes will help decision-makers propose changes in local, national and international policies, nurture the debate on the relationship between civil society and science and support the development of new RRI and open science strategies and guidelines". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/741677</p>	2017-2021	HORIZON	FUNDACION PRIVADA INSTITUTO DE SALUD GLOBAL BARCELONA, Spain

120	WeObserve: An Ecosystem of Citizen Observatories for Environmental Monitoring	<p>"Unleashing the power of the people. Citizen science, which involves engaging the general public in scientific research, has become increasingly popular in recent years. However, one challenge faced by citizen science initiatives is the lack of coordination, which can hinder the overall effectiveness of environmental monitoring efforts. In this context, the EU-funded WeObserve project aims to address three key challenges faced by Citizen Observatories (COs): awareness, acceptability and sustainability. By developing communities of practice, expanding knowledge sharing through toolkits and capacity development initiatives, and forging links with GEOS and Copernicus, WeObserve will strive to create a sustainable ecosystem of COs. This innovative approach has the potential to transform environmental management, empower resilient communities, and propel citizen science into the mainstream". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776740</p>	2017-2021	HORIZON	INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE, Austria
121	SMURBS: SMart URBan Solutions for air quality, disasters and city growth	<p>"According to UNs "World Urbanization Prospects: 2014 Revision" in today's increasingly global and interconnected world, over half of the world's population lives in urban areas, while the coming decades will bring further profound changes to the size and spatial distribution of the global population, also due to increasing migration processes. The continuing urbanization is projected to add 2.5 billion of urban population by 2050, and the world population living in cities to increase to 66%. Under these circumstances, sustainable development challenges will increasingly concentrate in cities". Source: https://www.copernicus.eu/en/smart-urban-solutions-air-quality-disasters-and-city-growth</p>	2017-2020	HORIZON	National Observatory of Athens, Greece
122	STARTS Prize: Grand prize of the European Commission honoring innovation in technology, industry and society stimulated by the arts	<p>"Science, technology and arts limn a nexus at which observers have identified extraordinarily high potential for innovation. And innovation is precisely what's called for if we're to master the social, ecological and economic challenges that Europe will be facing in the future. The STARTS Prize initiative will focus on the most forward looking collaborations at the crossings of art, science, technology, industry and society, will showcase achievements and encourage further collaborations and will honor the inspiring individuals and teams behind these achievements. Here, art is assigned the role of catalyst that propagates scientific and technological knowledge and skills among the general public and triggers innovative processes. Accordingly, the STARTS Prize is emphasizing, on one hand, artistic works that influence or change the way we look at technology, and, on the other hand, very promising forms of collaboration between the private sector and the world of art and culture. 8 prizewinning projects will be singled out for recognition in both categories and will be awarded each with €20,000. To provide the best possible environment for an international launch of the STARTS prize the project is linked to the PRIX ARS ELECTRONICA, one of the world's premier awards honoring creativity and innovativeness at the interface of art, technology, science and society. The collaboration with the renowned institutions Ars Electronica, Waag Society and BOZAR allows a fast introduction to the relevant communities on an international scale and provide the necessary expertise. Their large international network assures recruiting the best possible experts to ensure a high quality in the evaluation and selection of the prize winners. The presentation of the awards and the exhibition of the prize winning works at the Ars Electronica Festival, the BOZAR Electronic Art Festival, Waag Society and eight additional major events will foster a high interest and establish reputation for the STARTS prize". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/732019</p>	2017-2020	HORIZON	ARS ELECTRONICA LINZ GMBH & CO KG, Austria
123	ECSAnVis: Extreme Citizen Science: Analysis and Visualisation	<p>"The challenge of Extreme Citizen Science is to enable any community, regardless of literacy or education, to initiate, run, and use the result of a local citizen science activity, so they can be empowered to address and solve issues that concern them. Citizen Science is understood here as the participation of members of the public in a scientific project, from shaping the question, to collecting the data, analysing it and using the knowledge that emerges from it. Over the past 3 years, under the leadership of Prof. Muki Haklay, the Extreme Citizen Science programme at UCL has demonstrated that non-literate people and those with limited technical literacy can participate in formulating research questions and collecting the data that is important to them. Extreme Citizen Science: Analysis and Visualisation (ECSAnVis) takes the next ambitious step – developing geographical analysis and visualisation tools that can be used, successfully, by people with limited literacy, in a culturally appropriate way. At the core of the proposal is the imperative to see technology as part of socially embedded practices and culture and avoid 'technical fixes". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/694767</p>	2016-2022	ERC	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON, United Kingdom
124	CSA Oceans 2: Coordination action in support of the implementation of the Joint Programming Initiative on 'Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans'	<p>"CSA Oceans 2 is a 36 month project with the general aim to facilitate and support the implementation of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of JPI Oceans. CSA Oceans 2 will build further on the outcomes of the FP7 CSA Oceans project". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/696324</p>	2016-2019	HORIZON	SERVICE PUBLIC FEDERAL DE PROGRAMMATION POLITIQUE SCIENTIFIQUE, Belgium

125	DITOs: Doing It Together science	"Our project, 'Doing-It-Together Science', DITOs, represents a step change in European public engagement with science and innovation. We propose moving from a model in which scientific research, innovation, and problem-solving is mainly driven by scientific/professional institutions to one based on active public participation and capacity building with various levels and strategies of engagement in the scientific process. At the core of our ethos is a recognition of people's existing expertise and the different ways people want to and do engage in science and technology. The project is aimed at elevating public engagement with science across Europe from passive engagement with the process of developing science to an active one. Citizen Science and Do It Yourself (DIY) scientific efforts demonstrate that this is possible, and our aim is to ensure that the European Research Area will become leader in 'deep' public engagement that is afforded by these advances". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/709443	2016-2019	HORIZON	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON, United Kingdom
126	SeaChange	"The overarching goals of the Sea Change project are to bring about a fundamental "Sea Change" in the way European citizens view their relationship with the sea, by empowering them – as 'Ocean Literate' citizens - to take direct and sustainable action towards healthy seas and ocean, healthy communities and ultimately - a healthy planet". Source: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/652644	2015-2018	HORIZON	MARINE BIOLOGICAL ASSOCIATION OF THE UNITED KINGDOM, United Kingdom
127	Tentacular Thinking. Experiencing underwater assemblages of culture and nature	"Tentacular Thinking project aims to expand, amplify and widespread our sustainability message by realising a new visual-tactile experience on a forefront topic in scientific research (i.e. the new biodiversity patterns that have evolved to live on microplastics in marine environments) and by adopting an innovative "participatory art" approach, bringing about a deep engagement of people with the represented issue". Source: https://crowdusg.net/tentacular-thinking/	2024	EU program Culture Moves Europe	Raw-News and Platoon Cultural Development, Italy
128	FishArt: Participatory Art for environmental sustainability and aesthetic transformation of Anzio Fishermen's Harbour	"FishArt is a 10-month international project funded by the New European Bahahus Cross-KIC Connect 2024 written by and granted to Chiara Certoma' (UniTo – now at UniRm1) and led by Laura Corazza (UniTo), in collaboration with Raw-News, Platoon and the fishermen cooperatives of Anzio (Rome, Italy). FishArt promotes a radically participatory art and education process supporting the requalification of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy. FishArt is in the 2024 cohort of NEB Connect projects". Source: https://crowdusg.net/fishart/	2024	New European Bahahus Cross-KIC Connect 2024	University of Turin, Italy
129	#ItIsNotTooLate Seagrass Beds	"#ItIsNotTooLate Seagrass Beds is an eco-activist project for preservation and valorisation of seagrass as a source of marine life. Through research and knowledge transfer, public eco-actions and art installation, we aim to raise awareness of the local community and tourists about the importance of sea plants, create a lasting impact on the quality of life of the fish stock and the ecosystem, and build a sense of shared responsibility for the regeneration of our common natural environment". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/node/250565	2024	New European Bauhaus nominated for the Champions in the category Reconnecting with nature	Lončari, Croatia
130	Oceans sing, are you listening? Sounding out potentials for artistic audio engagements with science through the Polar Sounds project	"Acknowledgement of the growing crises facing our oceans has seen the increased visibility of watery spaces in policy initiatives and governance strategies. A good example is the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030). This international effort is designed to coordinate activities (from regional to national levels and beyond) that promote and develop knowledge of our seas and oceans to manage them for future generations. Societies everywhere, the Decade admits, are disconnected from these issues and despite the apparent growth of awareness (through popular televised documentaries and other public outputs that highlight the plight of ocean worlds) finding avenues to increase public understanding of ocean science in innovative and inspirational ways is being seen as critical for further engagement. In this article, we discuss efforts to connect society with the sea, focusing on how sound is a productive sensory medium for promoting ocean understanding. Drawing from a worldwide art-science collaboration, Polar Sounds, which united scientific acoustic data with musicians and sound artists around the globe, we make audible the potentials of embracing what is heard in our ocean worlds. The Ocean Decade alongside growing academic scholarship posits that ocean engagement, citizenship and connection is crucial to harness change that can improve the fate of flailing seas and that art-science collaborations can be crucial in building such bridges. We outline the Polar Sounds project, before arguing the need for further work that sounds out the potentials for engaging and inspiring alternative oceanic understandings and connections". Source: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308597X24003452#sec0030	2024	other	n/a
131	PescArt Menorca. Upcycling discarded fishing nets by artisans and artists from Menorca	"PescArt Menorca is a circular economy project whose objective is to promote the conversion of discarded fishing nets into new commercially viable products. The initiative seeks to reduce the significant environmental of this waste. The initiative aims to restore value to waste, promoting the symbiosis between the environment preservation and the local productive sector, through cooperating with the fishing sector and key social actors". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/application/pescart-menorca-upcycling-fishing-nets	2024	Champions under New European Bauhaus Prizes	PescArt Menorca is a project of Plastic Free Menorca Alliance, promoted by Menorca Preservation, Obsam, OPlastic Menorca, GOB Menorca and Associació Leader Illa de Menorca

132	Hostraka - learn, dive, nourish	"It's time to be an active part of the change: Höstraka is the first floating resort focused on the protection of the marine ecosystem that demonstrates how a sustainable vision can coexist with an amazing navigation experience. Our inspiration came directly from the ocean, with the cleaning activity of oysters that are able to create pearls from something bad for them: we want people to learn from what nature has already proved, offering a sustainable pearl experience". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/application/hostraka	2024	Rising Stars under New European Bauhaus Prizes	Students from Politecnico di Milano with the supervision of the tutor and professor Elena Elgani
133	Vantaa Art Routes	" We have created four art routes, that bring forth all the street art, public art and local history and culture of city districts that are otherwise left outside the spotlight of media or city communications. These are suburbs from the 70's that lack roots but offer great content to those who venture out to find it. Our art routes encourage others to visit and locals to be proud of what their suburb has to offer". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/application/vantaa-art-routes	2024	Champions under New European Bauhaus Prizes	Four suburbs in the city of Vantaa: Hakunila, Länsimäki, Koivukylä-Havukoski and Martinlaakso, Finland
134	Hydroscape Lisbon: Greening Lisbon's harbour and celebrating urban water and its processes.	" Lisbon is characterised by the river Tagus, watercourses and its topography. The project, consists of the design of an urban park and a water treatment center opening the harbour to the public, celebrating urban water resources and bringing attention to important issues of urban living and sustainability. How can water, act as a future tool for climate change, a binder and public space for Lisbon? The aim is to reformulate the relationship with water in a territorial as well as human scale". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/node/250954	2024	Rising Stars under New European Bauhaus Prizes	A young architect
135	Schelde Ensemble	" Schelde Ensemble is a design research that empowers human and non-human voices of the Dutch Southwest delta region. The project manifests itself in different outcomes: ranging from a permanent installation in a museum to a "landscape makers congress" for (local) civil servants, scientists, (landscape) designers and citizens. Schelde Ensemble challenges participants to listen, represent and negotiate their collective future in relation to the climate challenges of the region". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/node/250876	2024	Rising Stars under New European Bauhaus Prizes	The Netherlands
136	Destination Earth	" Destination Earth is a multi-sensory installation revealing the connection that ties atmosphere and ocean, humans and inhabitants of the sea, into a flow of interconnected motions. Warming waters and changes in the overall water circulation are impacting sound propagation in the ocean, sea mammal migratory patterns and survival, influencing in return our climate and the air we breathe every day. At the intersection of art, science and technology, Destination Earth explores the potential of Leonardo's supercomputer technology in the development of an ocean model combining flows, sea mammals communication, and ship activity through real-time visualization, generative sonification ,and audience participatory interaction. Performers invite audiences during their visit to support the 'regeneration' of oceans through their slowed down walking pattern and breath. Destination Earth supports an urgent international societal challenge by providing an embodied understanding of possible respectful living with ocean species. Leveraging the power of participatory performance and real-time generative composition to showcase the interdependence of cycles, flow dynamics and sound, the project's goal is to enable a sensory understanding of the changes in human motions required for our planet's survival". Source: https://archive.aec.at/startsprize/288297/	2024	S+T+ARTS Prize – Grand prize of the European Commission	n/a
137	Entangled Shorelines	Entangled Shorelines trajectory, source: https://research.hanze.nl/en/activities/entangled-shorelines-carry-me-across-the-sea	2024	other	n/a
138	SeaPaCS: Participatory Citizen Science against Marine Pollution	" SeaPaCS proposes a participatory citizen science (CS) project led by social and natural scientists that mobilises volunteers in data collection, elaboration and sharing on the biological consequences of marine plastic pollution (via in-situ samples collection for plastisphere DNA analysis, underwater video documentation of new ecological niches, plankton evaluation), and in drafting a plan for sustainability-oriented practices based on interviews with fishermen and sailors, in the coastal city of Anzio (Italy) on the Mediterranean Sea". Source: https://crowdusg.net/seapacs/	2023	IMPETUS Accelerator grant	DIGGEO@ESOMAS laboratory, University of Turin, Italy
139	"From Sea to Street"	" "From Sea to Street" is a citizen science initiative (CSI) aimed at addressing key challenges facing the ocean (marine ecosystem) today. The project answers the question of whether and how murals, a specific form of street art, can inspire people to take care of coastal and ecosystems and their sustainable use in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)". Source: https://impetus4cs.eu/from-sea-to-street/#:~:text=The%20interdisciplinary%20team%20saw%20murals,make%20this%20idea%20a%20reality "	2023	IMPETUS Accelerator grant	University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain

140	Ocean Routes	<p>"Exploring and valuing the maritime culture of Esposende – An ocean literacy and citizen science approach Ocean Routes was an ambitious and comprehensive project that mobilized a local school community together with local oceanic agents, towards an increased awareness and protection of Esposende Municipality maritime culture and ecosystem, in northern coastal Portugal, within a Natura 2000 site.</p> <p>The Ocean Routes project was anchored in six 'routes' representative of relevant ocean literacy topics in this territory (civilisations and history; gastronomy; biodiversity; sports; literature and music; future and sustainability), allowing to establish reciprocal benefits with existing curricular contents. Central to setting-up these knowledge routes was a citizen science approach, from data collection to analysis, by implementing 89 field sessions, directly and regularly by 1327 students (6-15 years old), together with 163 teachers, feeding the activities of 12 disciplines and 6 citizen science platforms. It was also the first opportunity to bring together 11 local oceanic stakeholders as a way to unlock their knowledge". Source: https://ars.electronica.art/citizenscience/en/ocean-routes/</p>	2023	European Union Prize for Citizen Science – Honorary Mentions	Rio Neiva – Environmental NGO, Portugal, António Rodrigues Sampaio School Group, Portugal
141	Project Poseidon	<p>"Project Poseidon brings NGOs, as well as researchers, refugees and locals together. Citizens will collect and monitor plastic pollution accumulating in the beach wrack of the Posidonia oceanica seagrass, the "lungs of the Mediterranean", for the critical ecosystem services it provides". Source: https://impetus4cs.eu/project-poseidon/</p>	2023	IMPETUS Accelerator grant	Malta Chamber of Scientists, Malt
142	REKNOTTING MARINE BIODIVERSITY	<p>"Coastal peripheries host overwhelming cultural heritage and pristine natural habitats, but they can be demographically and economically depressed and weakly monitored by marine ecologists. In some of these localities, local sailors are focal nodes of interpersonal networks, conduct recreational activities with tourists, run educational projects involving schools, and are enthusiastic promoters of ocean literacy". Source: https://impetus4cs.eu/biomarcs-reknotting-marine-biodiversity/</p>	2023	IMPETUS Accelerator grant	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohm, Italy
143	Whale Track	<p>"Whale Track provides a quick and easy way for the public to record and submit their sightings of whales, dolphins, and porpoises in Scottish waters. It is the first UK based biological recording app to use GPS tracking technology at sea. Designed to work even in the most remote areas, without network coverage or internet, it allows anyone to contribute to our research, from fishermen to tourists". Source: https://ars.electronica.art/citizenscience/en/whale-track/</p>	2023	IMPETUS Prize honorary mention	Hebridean Whale & Dolphin Trust, United Kingdom
144	Danube Design Lab Ruse	<p>"The Danube Design Lab empowers disadvantaged students from vocational schools to create new, sustainable public spaces along the Danube river in Ruse (Bulgaria). This provides opportunities for these often disenfranchised young people to be more included socially and develop professional networks. Each pop up architectural creation - made with recyclable materials such as wood, metal, fabric and mulch - allows residents to mingle, enjoy art together and reconnect with a part of the riverside that was long neglected". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/node/250469</p>	2023	New European Bauhaus Prize	"The Collective" Foundation, Bulgaria
145	Regeneration of beach dune systems	<p>"The project for the improvement and protection of the dune systems on the metropolitan beaches is a measure to mitigate the effects of climate change, especially along 17 kilometres of coastline in the south of Barcelona, which are part of the Llobregat River Delta (in Castelldefels, Gavà, Viladecans and El Prat de Llobregat). It is part of the integrated management of metropolitan beaches undertaken by the Barcelona Metropolitan Area (AMB), a supra-municipal government body that provides support for the municipalities in the Barcelona metropolis. It consists of a series of actions carried out since 2014, aimed at regenerating, protecting and improving these spaces, and changing people's perception to reinforce their attachment to the beaches, recognising them as local natural areas with many values. The project, based from the outset on public participation, includes the recreational use of beaches, since they are the most visited public space in Catalonia, with more than 80% of visitors being local residents.". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/node/255017</p>	2022	Winner under New European Bauhaus Prizes	Spain
146	Points of Life: co-constructing fragments in a shifting Lagoon	<p>"This residency explores nature-based solutions for the regeneration of the Venetian Lagoon". Source: https://starts.eu/challenge-venetian-lagoon-s4w/</p>	2022	S+T+ARTS Residency	n/a
147	Watercapitalism	<p>"The purpose of this residency is to design and restore the deep interconnections between human needs, economic well-being, the historical meaning-making across generations and the viability of water ecosystems". Source: https://starts.eu/challenge-water-capitalism-s4w/</p>	2022	S+T+ARTS Residency	n/a

148	Kama Muta (≈ Being Moved) Helps Connect People in and to Nature: A Photo Elicitation Approach	<p>“Kama muta is a social relational emotion, which English speakers often label as being moved or touched. Despite its important role for connecting to other human beings, its significance has not yet been explored in the context of nature. This qualitative study is the first to use photo elicitation to investigate a distinct emotion in the context of outdoor nature experiences. Specifically, we explored the emotion of kama muta and its role for connecting in and to nature. University students (N=27) were provided with disposable cameras and asked to take photographs of significant moments during their time in the outdoors. In follow-up interviews, participants talked about their experiences using their own photographs (N=559) as prompts. Photo elicitation was found to be an effective catalyst for participants to recall and report their emotional experiences. Thematic analysis of the interview transcripts and 108 photographs identified four main themes that highlighted kama muta: connecting (1) to others, (2) to nature, (3) to human-made material, and (4) the self. These findings applied to both outdoor nature experiences relatively close to city and relatively far from city. Future research should focus on the interaction of kama muta and other social relational emotions, such as awe, when further investigating the pathways that lead to nature connectedness and well-being”. Source: https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/eco.2020.0032</p>	2021	other	n/a
149	Stories from the Sea: Working with the SDGs in a Community-Based Art Workshop	<p>“This paper presents a series of community-based art workshops held in the summer of 2019 in Icelandic coastal villages on the theme Stories of the Sea. The collaborative project was aimed at providing meaningful aesthetic experiences based on contemporary art approaches that might not otherwise be readily available in peripheral communities. It was funded by the Icelandic Children’s Fund and attracted over 500 participants. Its underlying rationale was that art projects and artworks can be used to promote awareness of vices and virtues in order to open up ethical questions and criteria for practice concerning issues of sustainability. It thus focused on providing inspiring learning settings in which the transformative power of creativity might be used to raise environmental awareness, including the protection of the oceans. The pedagogical approaches used included participatory pedagogy, critical place-based learning and an emphasis on working with tacit knowledge already available in these localities. The project’s methodology was based on the five key dimensions of sustainable pedagogy (content, perspectives, process, context and design) while its findings were analyzed using the approach of art-based action research”. Source: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-16-3452-9_7</p>	2021	other	n/a
150	Examining the Potential of Art-Science Collaborations in the Anthropocene: A Case Study of Catching a Wave	<p>“There is a disconnect between ambition and achievement of the UN Agenda 2030 and associated Sustainable Development Goals that is especially apparent when it comes to ocean and coastal health. While scientific knowledge is critical to confront and resolve contradictions that reproduce unsustainable practices at the coast and to spark global societal change toward sustainability, it is not enough in itself to catalyze large scale behavioral change. People learn, understand and generate knowledge in different ways according to their experiences, perspectives, and culture, amongst others, which shape responses and willingness to alter behavior. Historically, there has been a strong connection between art and science, both of which share a common goal to understand and describe the world around us as well as provide avenues for communication and enquiry. This connection provides a clear avenue for engaging multiple audiences at once, evoking emotion and intuition to trigger stronger motivations for change. There is an urgent need to rupture the engrained status quo of disciplinary divisions across academia and society to generate transdisciplinary approaches to global environmental challenges. This paper describes the evolution of an art-science collaboration (Catching a Wave) designed to galvanize change in the Anthropocene era by creating discourse drivers for transformations that are more centered on society rather than the more traditional science-policy-practice nexus”. Source: https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/marine-science/articles/10.3389/fmars.2020.00340/full</p>	2020	other	n/a

151	The role of the arts in coping with place change at the coast	<p>"This paper explores the role of the arts in people's coping with (potential) place change at the coast in light of wind energy developments. In doing so, we elaborate on the effects of the arts on people's emotional connections to the landscape; the memories, beliefs, meaning and knowledge they associate with the landscape; and the expression of people's attachments through actions. We draw on 28 walking interviews and three group discussions which were conducted in Pingjum, a village along the Dutch Wadden Sea coast. A key feature in Pingjum's landscape is the Gouden Halsband, a late medieval dike surrounding the village. Recently, the area around Pingjum (including this dike) was designated as a potential location for the construction of a new windfarm. In our study, we found that the arts in Pingjum fuelled people's emotional connection to their (coastal) landscape and the Gouden Halsband, enhanced their knowledge of both and triggered them to reflect on the meanings they assign to them. In addition, the arts enhanced people's awareness and stimulated their assessment of the windfarm plans. The arts framed people's interpretation of the windfarm plans, mainly bringing potential negative impacts on the landscape to their attention. In this way, the arts encouraged action, stimulating both efforts to preserve the Gouden Halsband and protests against the proposed windfarm plans".</p> <p>Source: https://rgs-ibg.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/area.12417 "</p>	2018	other	n/a
152	I am the Ocean – arts and sciences to move from ocean literacy to passion for the ocean	<p>"Recent events in world politics demonstrate that a part of society has lost faith in their institutions. The importance of facts and evidence in citizens' decision making is weakened by opinions and belief systems. This post-fact or alternate facts era is a new challenge in the field of science communication as we urgently need to tackle global environmental challenges. Not only do scientists need to better communicate their work, they also need to explore alternative ways of transferring knowledge to help citizens reconnect with nature and actively take responsible decisions to protect it. The activity 'I am the Ocean' has been developed by an artist and a scientist with the goal to help students understand, connect and be equipped to take actions on marine global changes. The activity was a mix of field trips, open discussions and sensory immersion. It illustrates how art and metaphors can add an emotional and physical dimension to science communication, allowing a better understanding of otherwise invisible threats, and move from knowledge to passion".</p> <p>Source: https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315417000376</p>	2017	other	n/a
153	Sgeulachdan na Mara - Sea Stories	<p>"Sgeulachdan na Mara - Sea Stories grew out of collaborative research undertaken by social ecologists Ruth Brennan and Iain MacKinnon and audio-visual material generated by artist Stephen Hurrell, for the publication Dùthchas na Mara/Belonging to the Sea (Authors: MacKinnon and Brennan. Photographs: Hurrell). The idea of a dynamic map - to reflect intergenerational knowledge, fishermen's ways of knowing the sea and the intangible cultural heritage* of the marine environment - had been discussed by Brennan and MacKinnon, and Hurrell proposed the idea of an interactive digital map. This was subsequently developed by Hurrell and Brennan as a way of bringing to life, and making visible, what is often invisible to most people. Hurrell and Brennan decided to collaborate on a Barra-related project following their participation in Cape Farewell's Scottish Islands Expedition 2011. Following on from the Barra projects they received an award from Imagining Natural Scotland in 2013 to collaborate on producing a short film in response to the Firth of Clyde, titled Clyde Reflections, which they are currently working on. *The UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage 2003 provides international protection for the intangible aspects of cultural diversity".</p> <p>Source: https://www.mappingthesea.net/barra/</p>	2013	Creative Scotland 'First In A Lifetime' Award and additional funding from Comunn na Gàidhlig	n/a
154	The 432Hz project	<p>"432Hz - Cultural Association for Arts and Sciences is an entity from the island of São Miguel that is committed to promoting art and science as a means of expression, reflection and enrichment of society's literacy". Source: https://project432hz.webnode.pt/sobre-nos/</p>	n/a	other	n/a
155	Evoking the arctic spirit	<p>"Archival glacial survey photographs, AI generated moving image including the Inuit throat singer Annie Aningmiuq's 'Evoking the ice spirit'". Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lzOSKkKcTjo</p>	n/a	other	n/a

Information table

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TIDAL Arts

Transforming and Inspiring
Aquatic Landscapes Through
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